

Deakin University
Faculty of Education

Principles and practices of the process-conference approach to writing

**An investigation of the beliefs and strategies of four Victorian teachers
conducting exemplary writing programs**

Emi Emilia

**A research paper submitted in partial fulfilment
of the requirements for the degree of Master of Education at Deakin University**

September, 1996

Deakin University

Candidate's statement

I certify that the research paper entitled *Principles and practices of the process-conference approach to writing. An investigation of the beliefs and strategies of four Victorian teachers conducting exemplary writing programs*, and submitted for the degree of Master of Education is the result of my own work, and that this research paper (or any part of the same) has not been submitted for a higher degree to any other university or institution.

Signed:

Date:

Acknowledgments

My thanks are due to the Principals of the schools in which I conducted the research, and to the teachers who participated in this research, and who so willingly allowed me to observe their class and spent their time on answering questions of the interview; to the students who allowed me to take their writings as examples; to Howard Mould, for his patience in supervising this research paper and his sincere, priceless suggestions and advice; to Prof. Ian Ball, who has supervised this paper in terms of methodology of the research and Prof. Marie Emmitt for her guidance.

My special thanks goes to Tizani and Mizan, and my parents and sisters who have always supported me to study in Australia.

Contents

Abstract		v
Chapter 1	Introduction	1
Chapter 2	Literature Review	5
	The value of writing	5
	Popular approaches to teaching writing in Australia	8
	The process-conference approach	8
	Several conditions in the process-conference writing classroom	27
	Criticisms of the process-conference approach	28
	The genre-based approach	32
	Criticisms of the genre-based approach	36
Chapter 3	Research Method	38
	The study	38
	Purposes of the study	38
	Research questions	39
	Research method	39
	Procedure for analysing data	46
Chapter 4	Results	47
	Teachers' beliefs and understandings about the process-conference approach	47
	Teachers' beliefs concerning the criticisms made of the process-conference approach	52
	Application of the basic tenets of the process-conference approach	58
Chapter 5	Discussion of Results	79
	Teachers' beliefs and understandings about the process-conference approach	79
	Teachers' beliefs concerning the criticisms made of the process conference approach	84
	Application of the basic tenets of the process-conference approach	88
Chapter 6	Conclusions and Implications for Future Research	96
Chapter 7	Summary	102
	Bibliography	103
Appendix	Teachers' Responses to The Interview	112

Abstract

This study investigated the teachers' beliefs and understandings about the process-conference approach, their beliefs concerning the criticisms made of the process-conference approach, and how they applied the basic tenets of the approach in their writing classrooms.

This study involved four teachers, two teachers of grade 1, one teacher of a grade 3/4 and one teacher of a grade 5/6. Three teachers were from the same primary school, and one grade 1 teacher from another primary school, where the process-conference approach was used by the teachers. Interviews and participant observation were employed to obtain the data, which were then analysed and interpreted by the researcher. A triangulation (a comparison and a contrast of the data obtained from the various data collection techniques) was also made. To promote the validity of the research, the researcher has confirmed her interpretation of the data with the teachers.

The study found that the teachers' beliefs and understandings about the process conference approach were very strong. Their principles of teaching writing were consistent with the writings and suggestions by the advocates of the approach. Furthermore, the teachers' stated principles matched their practices in the classrooms.

Of the criticisms investigated in this study, only one criticism was believed to be justified by all teachers, namely that "the free choice of topics creates gender stereotypical writings." Other criticisms investigated in this study were not believed to be valid by the teachers and were not evident in practice.

The results of the research were encouraging to the researcher who wants to implement the approach in Indonesia. The process-conference approach is indeed worth introducing and applying in Indonesian schools to help children increase their success in learning.

With the emphasis on authorship as well as the mechanics of writing, the process-conference approach allows children to develop not only as scribes, but also as authors. Writing in a variety of genres also enables children to develop writing not only for the satisfaction of personal needs, such as writing personal recounts, but also for the fulfilment of their social needs, such as to keep in touch with other people (writing letters), and to gain and to handle information (writing reports, essays and instructions). Confidence and competence in writing the various genres can empower students not only in their access to, and their success in higher levels of education, but also in their daily living.

Chapter 1

Introduction

Writing is central to education. That is why it is not surprising that it has received a great deal of attention from theorists concerned with how we teach writing.

During the last three decades, there have been many changes in the teaching of writing in Australia. Teachers and researchers have shifted from focusing on teaching writing as product to teaching writing as process; to creating texts. Much research has been done which has shifted its focus on the study of writing, away from the product, and on to the process. The teachers' belief that children cannot write until after they are able to read has also changed, and now they encourage children to write from an early age. Children are now considered to be able and willing to write.

Graves (quoted by Turbill, 1982), one of the pioneers of the process approach to writing, says:

Children want to write. For years we have underestimated their urge to make marks on paper. We have underestimated that urge because of a lack of understanding of the writing process, and what children do in order to control it. Without realising it, we wrest control away from the children and place road blocks that thwart their intentions. Then we say, 'They don't want to write. What is a good way to motivate them?' ... If children are to be in control in their writing we need to give them more opportunity to write, allow them to write about what they know, allow them to choose the materials they want to write with (pencil, crayon, large paper, lined paper, etc.), and allow them the opportunity to write for themselves initially (a draft copy) (1982, p.11).

Jensen, to quote Elbow, says: "Writing is the gateway to literacy, not reading. Writing is the realm where children can attain literacy first and best feel on top of it - feel ownership and control over the written word" (1993, p. 2). Harste, Woodward & Burke (1984), in reporting their research on the authoring cycle of literacy, point out that children can write long before they enter school. They cite Halliday, as saying:

A child doesn't need to know any linguistics in order to use language to learn; but a teacher needs to know some linguistics if he wants to understand how the process takes place - or what is going wrong when it doesn't (1984, p. ix).

In addition, the notion that we have to get our writing right in the first draft or that we are a failure, we can not write, which has made generations of children decide they can not write, has almost disappeared. All these changes are reflected in curriculum documents and in materials published for classroom activities. Many reviews, special issues of journals and conferences have been devoted to the topic of the process a writer goes through when writing. There are even whole books devoted to discussing the process of writing and its application in the classroom.

Calkins (1986) describes these changes as *a paradigm shift: from products to process*, and says that in the past writing was rarely taught, and the teacher emphasised products, not the process that produced them. Teachers' emphases were on categorising written products, the characteristics of expository, persuasive, descriptive, etc. Teachers never watched the children write, or spoke with them about their composing strategies, and how much time they spent on writing. She says:

The dominant method of composition instruction since the late nineteenth century has been to describe and differentiate the modes of discourse, and to show models of each mode. But recently, the field has undergone a paradigm shift. Now, instead of asking only 'What are the forms of good writing?' many teachers and researchers ask 'What processes do writers use?', 'What do children do when they write and how do these behaviours change as they grow older?', and 'How do the behaviours of skilled and unskilled writers differ?' The focus has shifted from products to processes (Calkins, 1986, p. 14).

Furthermore, despite the importance of the correct spelling, punctuation, capitalisation, and all the characteristics of ideal finished products, teachers now realise that it was misleading to have emphasised the form of writing first rather than the function or content. Writers do not begin writing by saying "I want to write a three paragraph persuasive essay", instead, they begin with saying "I need to convince people to" Teachers now realise that knowing the characteristics of ideal finished products has little to do with developing the skills to produce those products (Calkins, 1986).

Jensen (1993, p. 2) says:

We now know that (1) writing during the early years is a natural gateway to literacy; (2) all children can be writers; (3) understanding writing and writers means understanding complex and interrelated influences - cognitive, social, cultural, psychological, linguistic, and technological; and (4) we write so that both we and others can know what we think, who we are.

It was particularly thanks to the studies done by Britton, Burgess, Martin, McLeod & Rosen (1975) and Graves (1983) that the focus on the study and the teaching of writing shifted from product to process. Britton *et al* (1975, p. 21) say:

Teachers have many reasons for being interested in writing processes. Their involvement with all the learning processes of their pupils requires that they understand how something came to be written, not just what is written. They can bring to their reading of a pupil's work all their knowledge of his life and his context, realising, perhaps intuitively, that what they already know about a child and his thinking when they read his work enables them to understand and appreciate something that may be incomprehensible to another...

Similarly, Walshe (1980, p. 81), quotes Clapp (1975) as saying that "teacher's understanding of the writing process is basic to any teacher's effort to help students improve as writers."

The success of the teaching writing based on the process approach has been reported by many researchers and writers. It has had a positive effect on the teaching of writing and the attitude to writing on the part of both teachers and students. Writing has now become something that children are looking forward to and teachers have become more interested in reading what their students are writing (Collerson, 1989a).

Turbill and Butler (1984, p. 2) state:

The teaching of writing in Australia ... has undergone exciting changes as more and more teachers have become aware of the great benefits of adopting a 'process-conference' approach. They have realised that once the act of writing is seen as a process, (rather than a product), then it makes sense to allow children to write creatively as professional authors do, through a process which includes drafting, revising, editing, and polishing with possible publication (and therefore an audience) in view.

The success reported by the researchers and the result of the process-conference approach that I noticed during my classroom observations in several primary schools in Australia, in Victoria in particular, during which I was really impressed with the students' writing ability and self confidence in their writing, have made me increasingly eager to look more closely at this approach, and to discover and record how teachers use it in practice to help children develop their writing ability. I have no

doubt that it would be of great benefit if Indonesian primary teachers are introduced to this approach, to help Indonesian children increase their success in learning.

However, like other methods, this process-conference approach to teaching writing is not exempt from criticisms, and there have been several criticisms, particularly coming from those who advocate the genre approach as discussed in chapter 2. These criticisms include:

1. Process writing comes to be mainly story writing, and the process approach is not applied when writing in other curriculum areas, like science or social studies (Collerson, 1989a).
2. Free choice in the process writing class creates gender stereotypes, dominant social stereotypes and biases (Kamler, 1992; 1993).
3. Children can not be treated as professional writers, because in the stage of revising, children can not revise their writing. Even when they can detect their problems, most of these problems can not be corrected (Bartlett, 1982).
4. The process approach advantages only a certain group of children (Martin, in Richardson, 1991).
5. Ownership and individualised writing program ignore the fact that writing is a social construct (Gilbert, 1990), and ignores the fact that the goal of literacy is always societal (Edelsky, 1994).

This study examined the teachers' beliefs and understandings about the process-conference approach to writing, the teachers' beliefs concerning the criticisms made of the process approach, and how they applied the basic tenets of the approach in their classrooms.

The result of this research would be of great value as a basis to introducing the process-conference approach to Indonesian teachers, and to demonstrate that the process-conference approach is an educational program which is worth implementing in Indonesia.

Chapter 2

Literature Review

The literature on the process-conference approach is extensive; a number of aspects of the literature were identified as relevant to this research, including the value of writing, popular approaches to teaching writing in Australia, namely: the process-conference approach and the genre-based approach, including the criticisms of these approaches. The literature review is summarised under the following headings:

- The value of writing

- Popular approaches to teaching writing in Australia:

- The process-conference approach

- Several conditions in the process-conference writing classroom

- Criticisms of the process-conference approach

- The genre-based approach

- Criticisms of the genre-based approach.

The Value of Writing

Writing, as stated in the first chapter, plays a very important role in everyday life of schooling. It can reflect what children know, what they want to know, what they learn and what they have learnt. Skill in writing is a key factor for students to succeed in school. In examinations, for example, it has been demonstrated that “students who do well at exams are almost always the confident writers” (Walshe, Sherley & O’Meara 1984, p. 33). Thomson (1978) argues that based on the amount of writing done by students at school, it cannot be denied that writing makes a significant contribution to their learning in all parts in all key learning areas of the curriculum. He says that writing activities should be organised in such a way as to make an optimum contribution to students’ learning.

Writing is also important for someone's personal development, as writing can give her/him joy, different tastes of life, self confidence and pride. Walshe (1981) contends that the role of writing in personal development is very important. He states:

... in fact, whenever children (or adults) are allowed to write about their own experiences, they engage in an original and creative process: they compose their ideas, feelings, fears and hopes - and so, of course compose themselves, strengthening identity, self image, self reliance. ... To searchingly construe experience through writing is one of the best ways in which children can act for growth upon themselves (Walshe, 1981, p. 146).

Calkins (1986) states that human beings have a deep need to represent their experiences through writing because through writing we can turn the chaos into something beautiful, to frame selected moments in our lives, to uncover and celebrate the organising patterns of our existence. She then quotes Anne Morrow Lindbergh, who says: "I must write, I must write at all costs. For writing is more than living, it is being conscious of living" (Calkins, 1986, p. 3).

Writing can also empower someone, as the ability to write can offer him/her a better life and position in the society, because those who are able to write are generally the ones who can get more access to education which, in our society, as Moss says, "leads to a more secure and even influential life" (1981, p. 119). Writers are generally considered as the ones who can herald ideas or inspirations which can influence the belief or attitude of the society towards something, someone or existing conditions in the community in general.

Graves (1984, p. 64) says, "Writing develops courage. Writers leave the shelter of anonymity and offer to public scrutiny their interior language, feelings, and thoughts. ... A writer is a person with his skin off." Furthermore, Anita Brookner says: "I started writing because of a terrible feeling of powerlessness" (cited by Murray, 1990, p. 4).

Writing is also thinking. Murray (1985, p. 3) writes:

The act of writing is an act of thought. Writing is not superficial to the intellectual life, but central to it; writing is one of the most disciplined ways of making meaning and one of the most effective methods we can use to monitor our own thinking. We write to think ...

Similarly, Emmitt & Pollock (1991) write about the important role that writing plays in the development of thinking and concepts. They say that writing gives us the time and opportunity for reflection; time, because the words are not gone as soon as uttered, opportunity, because they are fixed before us on the page so that we can consider them. In addition, due to the permanent nature of writing, it does develop our thinking more effectively. In the process of writing, we review our knowledge, actively apply our understanding, analyse and synthesise what we mean, and constantly evaluate the text we are composing as we move back and forth to create meaning for ourselves and others. Furthermore, writing allows ourselves as well as others to evaluate our ideas easily and their responses further enable us to change and develop our thinking.

Because writing is a thinking process, it should be central to school learning. In the English Curriculum and Standards Framework (Victorian Board of Studies 1995), it is stated that writing contributes not only to communication about texts read or viewed, but also to learning. Walshe (1986a) asserts that writing is the most powerful form of learning, and nearly all writing can have a component of both learning to write and writing to learn. Moreover, he writes, there are two remarkable learning powers brought into human affairs by writing. These are:

1. writing as the great collector of ideas - only writing can collect and store all the ideas that arise from reflection and talk, and
2. writing as the great clarifier of thinking - writing takes thought from the invisible mind and makes them visible on paper.

Coleman, Kalantzis, Kress, Martin, Poynting, Slade & Wignell (1987, p. 7) claim that "writing can be a powerful means of learning in all years, ... and in all curriculum areas. It can concentrate thought and facilitate investigate, critical and creative thinking." Walshe (1984, p. 15) writes: "Writing is a marvelous unifier. We teachers have to make proper use of its power in securing the deepest kinds of learning, in improving children's critical thinking, and in integrating the curriculum." In addition,

Rothery (1986b, p. 64) mentions: "In any given situation students are likely doing both writing to learn and learning to write."

Janet Emig considers that writing is a mode of learning, and she puts it:

Writing represents a unique mode of learning - not merely valuable, not merely special, but unique... Writing serves learning uniquely because writing as process and product possesses a cluster of attributes that correspond uniquely to certain powerful learning strategies (quoted by Walshe, 1981, p. 142).

In addition, Collerson (1989a, p. 1) states, "learning to write effectively is a very important part of our students' education and the ability to do so can be a great asset throughout their lives."

Finally, Turbill (1982, p. 47) says:

writing, regarded as a significant act of original thinking/ self-expression / communication, needs to be treated as part - and often the culminating part - of integrated learning. A child writing willingly is responding, integrating, making much of the experience of life, which is what the best learning is supposed to be all about.

Popular Approaches to Teaching Writing in Australia

- **The Process-Conference Approach**

In this approach, it is suggested that writing is taught as a process, and that children in the classroom should experience the process of writing as professional writers do, starting from choosing a topic, brainstorming, and moving to the publication of the product. The concepts underlying this approach are that "writing is a craft, so children must learn mainly by writing itself" (Walshe, 1981, p. 147), "writing is learned in the same way other activities are learned - by doing and by heeding what happens..." (Moffett, 1983, p. 193).

Children learning to write under this approach, in addition to being encouraged to attempt any form of writing which may help them discover and communicate what

they have to say (Murray, 1982), should learn that writing "is a process in the sense that it involves thinking, feeling, talking, reading-and writing. It is an extended effort to make a message clear" (Turbill, 1983, p. 9), and "a process that they can use now and in the future - to produce whatever product his subjects and his audience demands" (Murray, 1982, p. 26). Children should also learn that professional writers do not do just a one-shot draft to make their message clear. Like professional writers, children need time and opportunity to think about what is to be written, to make decisions about the writing before, during and after drafting, and then to revise effectively so that the piece can be confidently presented to the intended reader with expectation of a positive response.

Walshe *et al* (1984, p. 32) suggest,

Never say, 'I can't write.' If you do say this, probably it's because you find that you can't 'get it right the first time'. Rest assured, no one can. Not even professional writers. Remember, writing is a deeper kind of thinking. It is the deepest study thinking you have to do. It certainly isn't a mechanical activity: it is a process. ... when you are asked to write..., you can't just toss off an instant essay; you, or any other writer, must think - write - revise ...

Teachers using this approach are advised to let the children write, read what they've written with the class, and to try to help each of them say what she/he has to say.

Murray (1982, p. 115) suggests:

The writing teacher must be prepared to diagnose their problem and respond to them, force them to take the initiative in the writing course, as the course is most successful when students discover their own problems, and when they discover their own solutions. The teacher should create the climate in which the process of writing can take place and teachers succeed the most when they interfere - or teach - the least.

The process of writing can generally be divided into three stages, which, according to Britton *et al* (1975), are conception, incubation, and production, and according to Walshe (1981) and Murray (1982) are prewriting, writing and rewriting (or Walshe mentions post-writing). Although the terms given by Britton *et al* (1975) are different from those by Walshe (1981) and Murray (1982), the process in each stage that a writer should pass through is actually the same, and the process which produces creative and functional writing is the same, and can be described as follows:

Prewriting

Prewriting is everything that takes place before the first draft. In this stage, a writer may do the following

- select a topic, or subject;
- brainstorm: which may include research, day-dreaming, note-making;
- decide the topic, spot an audience, choose a form which may carry his subject to his audience, and decide the purpose - whether to express her/himself, to provide information for the reader, or to create a literary work;
- outline: write down the main ideas.

In relation to this prewriting stage, Walshe mentions that before writing a writer should also have a need to write which "has its genesis in some encounter or experience of real life, something arising from seeing, doing, talking, reading and imagining" (1977, p. 84). In short, prewriting is a period rehearsing of what to say, and how, perhaps accompanied by talk, some reading, some drawing, and the jotting of notes - till at last the pen is taken up.

Writing

This stage includes:

- drafting: the act of producing a first draft, getting ideas onto paper in sentences and paragraphs, with the writer not unduly worrying about correct spelling and other mechanics of writing, for as Murray (1982) writes, mechanics come last. Harste *et al* (1984) also point out that during writing, the writer's attention must be focused on the creation of a text world - solving problems of unity and discontinuity between the text world and the real world, creating and searching for unity within the fictionalised world. They write: "To worry about correct spelling and good grammar is to occupy short-term memory with surface text, and in the process, to lose text" (1984, p. 140).

Drafting can perhaps be done swiftly, perhaps laboriously, but always with some intensity of intellectual and emotional involvement. This drafting can be done several times as most writers, even professional, cannot compose a paragraph or an essay well on the first attempt, as Kane (1983, p. 43) says: "We must write, rewrite it, do it again."

In helping children to produce messages at this stage, it is important, particularly in early levels, that the teacher encourages the children to learn spelling via spelling inventions (Graves, 1984c). Sowers reports that "invented spelling gives young writers early power ... They work like writers who don't stop to look up a word in the dictionary" (1984, p. 39).

- revising: meaning "seeing it again" (Walshe, 1981, p. 38). It is a second critical look or third or umpteenth. It is to see the writing as others will see it. This revising is very important in the process of writing, as Graves says: "writing becomes truly writing in revision. A professional first draft is often not much better than anyone else's. It is chiefly in revision that the professional's experience and craftsmanship show" (quoted by Walshe, 1981, p. 37).

To revise effectively, Kane (1983) says, forces the writer to read slowly, because revising is not simply correcting and polishing the draft. When a writer revises, s/he becomes a reader, a demanding reader who expects perfection, and the activities done during the revision, among others, are:

- adding - inserting needed words, sentences, paragraphs;
- cutting/deleting - getting rid of whatever goes off the topic or repeats what has already been said;
- changing/replacing - as needed, substituting new words, sentences, paragraphs, for what we have cut;
- sharpening punctuation to make reading easier;

- rearranging words, sentences or paragraphs to produce a more convincing order or sequence of explanation;
- correcting any slips or omission.

During the revision, the writer also has to think hard about the intended readers, about what will interest them, and a form of publication that will attract them.

In relation to the ability of children to revise their writing, Graves (1983) says that children already know how to revise before they come to school. When something is not satisfying to them, they change it. This, for example, can be seen when they are playing. They try to transform blocks, rearrange furniture in their toy house, etc. Moreover, Calkins, quoted by Graves (1984b), found that children's strategies in revision followed time-space development in a very consistent way, and based on her finding, she mentions four types of revisers.

Type 1: children who write successive drafts, without looking back to earlier drafts.

Type 2: children who keep refining earlier work but the refinement is of minor consequence. Some spelling, punctuation, of a word or two might be changed, but that is all. These children could come up with new information, but they could not insert the data in the text.

Type 3: children of this type are in the transition of type 2 and 4. These children move between periods when they refine drafts, and periods when they are abandoning them and beginning new ones. These children are able to insert new information to the text.

Type 4: for these children revision results from interaction between writer and draft, between writer and internalised audience, between writer and evolving subject. They reread to see what they have said and to discover what they want to say. There is a constant vying between intended meaning and discovered meaning, between the forward motion of making and the backward motion of assessing. These children immediately ask if they can change parts of it. One

change leads to another. Arrows, stars and carets are used to change and insert the information.

- editing: focusing on surface features (surface correctness and smoothness) and styling, which ensures conformity with the standards and conventions of writing (can be those observed by the particular publishers). When a writer edits, s/he pays attention to correct grammar, spelling, and punctuation, and to correct use of capitals, numbers in italics and abbreviations. Editing takes time and is very crucial in writing, as Troyka (1987) says that no matter how much attention a writer has paid to pre-writing, drafting and revising, slapdash editing will distract her/his readers.
- rehearsing: any looking ahead in the mind, and this may occur during drafting, and certainly during the revising a draft in order to discover what might be worked into the next draft. In this case, Calkins (1986) Stires (1989) and Graves (1989a) mention that children generally rehearse their writing by drawing, and Turbill (1982) reports that drawing is considered integral to the writing process which can be done before, during or after the writing. Calkins further says that “drawing has an important role to play. The act of drawing and the picture itself both provide supportive scaffolding within which the piece of writing can be constructed” (1986, p. 50).
- rewriting: the final writing in the form in which it is presented to the intended readers, and according to the best selling author Mario Puzo, “rewriting is the whole secret to writing” (cited by Walshe, 1981, p. 37). Rewriting is also reconsideration of subject, form, and audience. It is researching, rethinking, redesigning, rewriting - and finally, line-by-line editing, the demanding, satisfying process of making each word right.
- proofreading: simply the final checking of the written draft before presenting it to the readers. It results in a final, edited draft with repaired typographical or handwriting errors. It involves a careful line-by-line reading. While proofreading, a writer can

read the written draft slowly, quickly, silently, loudly, or s/he can also ask somebody else to proofread her/his writing.

Post-writing

Post-writing stage includes:

- publishing: "to make public"(Parry & Hornsby, 1985, p. 25). Publication is very important to make children realise that the real writing is never for exercise purposes only; it is always motivated by an audience (readers). In short, real writing is always intended for publication, not commercially of course, but to inform, persuade, or entertain someone. "Publication means getting writing to real readers - getting it read" (Turbill, 1982, p. 61).

Publication is also important in motivating children to write, because audience in which the prospect of publication exists is needed not only by professional writers, but also by children who are learning to write.

- response

Although the writing is finished, the writer wonders whether her/his writing has succeeded - she/he looks for a reaction or response that will let her/him know if her/his expression was effective or not. In relation to this response, Walshe says: "response is the part of the writing process which completes the post-writing stage. It is the end part, but it is also a new beginning, for the spirit engendered in the writer by the readers' response enters into the pre-writing stage of the next piece of writing" (1981, p. 53).

Moffett (1983) considers response to be important as part of the process of children's learning to use language, both in speech and in writing, by saying:

Learning to use language, then requires the particular feedback of human response, because it is to other people that we direct speech. The fact that one writes by oneself does not at all diminish the need for response, since one writes for others. Even when one purports to be

writing for oneself-for pure self-expression, if there is such a thing - one can not escape the ultimately social implications inherent in any use of language (Moffett, 1983, p. 191).

In relation to the process of writing described above, the amount of time a writer spends in each stage depends on her/his personality, her/his work habits, her/his maturity as a craftsman/woman, and the challenge of what s/he is trying to say. It is not a rigid lock-step process, but most writers most of the time pass through these three stages. In addition, as Murray (1985, p. 4) says, "the process is not linear, but recursive. The writer passes through the process once, or many times, emphasising different stages during each passage."

Murray (1985) also says that there is no one writing process. The writing process will change according to the cognitive style of the writer. Some of our students will move slowly and steadily, developing their writing by accretion. Others will plunge in, make leaps, skip back and forth. Neither process or all the range of processes in between is correct. Each writer will also have a range of varieties within the her/his own writing process, or will have entirely different processes.

Berthoff (1981) states, "The phases of the composing process are not distinct: they are dialectical; they are on again-off again. Revising, for instance, can, and I think should, continue right up until the last; introductions are seldom written first" (quoted by Bright, 1995, p. 9).

In teaching writing as a process, Graves (1983) suggests that the teacher should work together with the children, help children, say, choose the topic, revise, etc. The teacher should also give them a model of the process of writing, starting from telling what she/he is going to write, and why s/he chose the topic. Then the teacher can write on large sheets of paper, on an overhead projector, and so forth. These are expected to make children see or realise that there is a process of choosing a topic, writing, etc. Graves says:

Writing is a study subject. I invite children to do something I am already doing. Just as an artist in the studio paints alongside her students, I write along with her children. A piano teacher

may show his student how to play a particular passage, but occasionally, he plays an entire piece so that his student can experience the beauty of it (1994, p. 47).

In addition, Schroder & Lovett say:

By modeling how writing is done rather than simply evaluating a finished piece, teachers find that students enjoy writing and learn more from it; gradually children begin to write with greater interest and stronger voices and, with practice, to become more adept at writing mechanics (1993, p. 37).

Model writing is also considered to be a powerful strategy that can be used to demonstrate a range of skills, processes and strategies (Education Department of Western Australia, 1994a, p.15). It is further stated that:

Modelled writing gives children the opportunity to see the processes through which writers work. As teachers illustrate procedures through modelling, children see that writing is an interactive process; they are reassured that writers 'make mistakes'; they become aware of the processes of editing; and they develop confidence in using the processes themselves (Education Department of Western Australia, 1994a, p. 16).

In this approach teachers are also required to act as editors or tutors who, in individual or group conferences, help children to become aware of their own intentions as writers and at the same time to become aware of the needs of their readers as they begin and revise self selected and teacher-suggested pieces. Teachers are also required to be able to provide rich and varied reading and writing environments in which children become aware of different kinds of texts or genres. In addition, the approach requires teachers to become skilled and sensitive at asking questions that will lead to students being able to improve their own writing in the first place and then being able to ask the appropriate questions of their writing that will lead to improvement (Emmitt & Pollock, 1991).

In short, the teaching of writing under the process-conference approach focuses on what writers do in the process of moving towards the final product, and the attention is on the writer as language learner and creator of text, and on the content first, and then on the form. This does not mean that the form is less important, as Barton argues that "learning to write involves two aspects associated with the two meanings of the word

write: learning the mechanics of writing, or becoming a *scribe*, and deciding what to write, or becoming an *author*" (1994, p. 156).

In addition to the concept that *writing is treated as a process*, there are also some other basic tenets of the process-conference approach, which are also considered as its strengths. These are:

1. Generally free choice of topics

This tenet allows children to exercise power and control, as they take responsibility for their writing. Children are encouraged to write on the topic chosen by themselves, and the topics, as stated by Walshe (1986b) are almost always personal - what I did, what I know, the story I've made up. The idea behind this tenet is that "writing begins with all that we have known since we were born, and perhaps with a lot of knowledge that was born in us. We write, first of all to discover what we know and what we need to know"(Murray, 1984, p. 3).

Free choice of topic is very important, as free choice of topics enables children to write "what they know", which, according to Rosen (1989), from his experience being taught by his father when he was a child, is the key factor to his success in being a writer. He realises that when he writes, he should write only what he knows, as his father told him that he wouldn't be able to write something unless he knew it.

Similarly, Graves (1983, p. 13) says that "the easiest place for any writer to begin writing, ... is in writing about something you know," and he further says that "the most important thing children can learn is what they know and how they know it. Topic choice, a subject a child is aware that he [sic] knows something about, is at the heart of success in writing" (1983, p. 72). If children are to become independent learners, we have to help them know what they know; and this process begins with helping children to choose their own topics. Graves (1983, p. 21) states:

Writers who learn to choose topics well make the most significant growth in both information and skills at the point of best topic. With the best topic, the child exercises strongest control,

establishes ownership, and with ownership pride in the piece. ... (On the contrary) Children who are fed topics, story starters, lead sentences even opening paragraphs as a steady diet for three or four years, rightfully panic when topics have to come from them. Writers who do not learn to choose topics wisely lose out on the strong link between voice and subject.

Britton *et al* (1975, p. 23-24) put it this way:

Writing that is totally self-initiated is of great interest to us, not least because it provides an important link with mature adult writing. It is also likely to be accompanied by much greater involvement by the writer, and may have very much longer preparatory stages, and most of the processes mentioned here may be much more complex. ... However controlled the situation, the writer is selecting from what he knows and thinks (unless pure copying is all that's wanted) and embodying that knowledge and thought in words which he produces, no matter how much he draws on the language of a book or of the teacher's note. Many young writers realise their own need to be themselves in their writing, even within the framework provided for them. ... The writer, we are claiming, must relate his task, somewhere to his own hierarchical construct system.

Sealey, Sealey & Millmore (1979, p. vii) state:

Activities that encourage to communicate their own ideas, discoveries and feelings, particularly in written form, are a way of promoting rigorous learning. These activities give children a way to apply what they already know to what interests them and, in the process, they acquire new abilities. This is the essence of what we mean by adapting individuals-finding their capabilities at the start and building from there.

Furthermore, Taylor (1973, p.90), says "...nothing a child writes about is worth anything at all unless it has arisen from an experience in his [sic] rich learning environment." Then he quotes Lewis (1969), who says, "No one can doubt that a free choice of theme is a powerful incentive for a child in getting him [sic] to want to say something to others as well as he can" (1973, p. 90).

Gordon (1986) reports that free choice of topics allows the learning to be inclusive of all students, as each student's choice of topic and ownership of their own work, and her/his experience and language are respected and given values.

The concept of free choice of topics, however, should not be misunderstood. This free choice of topics is particularly applied in story writing, which is personal, and particularly emphasised in the early levels of schooling. Free choice of topics does not mean that the students choose their own topics every time they write. The teacher can

also generate and set topics, particularly when the students are involved in factual writing such as required in the key learning areas: science, history, etc.

Graves (1984a) has warned against turning the "free choice of topics" concept into a "dogma". He states:

Writers do need to learn to choose a topic, ..., learn what they know and present it to other audiences. The personal base is the base of voice. ... Still, there is an important place for the assigned topic; it belongs in the writer's diet.

About twenty percent of a writer's diet ought to be assigned. But an assigned topic requires preparation; it requires the writer to read, interview, find the voice of opinion and concern with wrestling with the facts. ...

Assigned topics can also be the short ten or twenty minute discovery of a new area in reading, or a précis as mentioned in the section on different uses of time for writing (1984a, p. 191-192).

Similarly, Collerson (1989b) suggests that it is sometimes necessary to provide children with a very carefully structured experience of some particular topic. He states:

It is important for children to learn to choose topics for their writing, ... because it is important for them to discover what they can write about and to have the experience of writing about things that they know and can write about with confidence.

Yet, children also need to learn how to write about things which they have not chosen for themselves, and to cope with topics which come to them in the course of their schooling (1989b, p. 110-111).

2. Daily writing time (minimum 4 days a week)

In this approach writing is not just an occasional once-a-week affair but an activity which children are able to practise everyday (Graves, 1985a). Graves (1983) states that one way to improve the quality of students' writing is to spend more time on composing and less time practising isolated skills, that is, punctuation, capitalisation, grammar, spelling, and legibility. Based on his research Graves recommends a minimum of four days a week to see any appreciable change in the quality of writing. It takes that amount of writing to contribute to the students' personal development as learners.

Unless children write at least 4 days a week, they won't like it. Once a week writing only reminds them they can't write; they never write often enough to listen to their writing. ... When they write regularly, papers accumulate, and there is visible evidence they know and

are growing. They gain experience in choosing topics and very soon have more topics to write about than class time can accommodate" (Graves, 1985a, p. 72).

Graves (1983) also says that it is only the regular practising of the process that will help children realise that not even the professionals can get their writing right straight off. Everyone needs to revise, and every one can revise - and that means every one can learn to write, and this would put an end to students' fear of writing.

According to Graves (1985a), regular writing helps:

- children choose topics;
- children listen to their pieces and revise;
- teachers help each other;
- teachers listen to child texts;
- skills develop in the context of child pieces;
- teachers to have greater access to children.

Calkins (1986) says that it is almost impossible to create an effective writing workshop if students write only once or twice a week. She writes that, if on Monday one student begins a piece about how he stayed overnight with a friend who lives in a private house, and he doesn't see that piece again until Friday, he will find it hard to sustain an interest in it, and harder still to remember the questions his friend asked during the conference. Writing, she says, "is like any sport. If we jog only once a week, it is hard to break the inertia brought on by six days of not jogging. But if we jog every day, it becomes easier and easier; we get into a rhythm, we find our stride. The same is true of writing" (1986, p. 25).

She suggests that writing time be scheduled regularly so that children can anticipate it. If children know that every morning will begin with an hour for writing, then they come to school ready to write, because children, like the rest of us, will write when they are not writing if writing becomes a regular and frequent part of their lives.

Egan (1984) finds out that by doing writing in every morning session, out of which all other language activities emerge, not only do the children write and draw keenly, but their reading test results improve. Moreover, spelling, handwriting, and the conventions get all the attention they need. And, of key importance, the children are regularly experiencing the process of drawing, drafting, revising, rewriting, and publishing.

Clark (1987), based on his experiences in teaching writing, concludes that daily writing in class helps students grow in all aspects of language study. A teacher who creates time in the curriculum for writing will strengthen children's skills in critical thinking, reading, listening, speaking, and grammar.

3. The Conference

The conference means there are opportunities for children to talk about their writing with other children, with the teacher or with another adult. This interaction may occur at any stage in the process - even before the writing has begun (Graves, 1983). In the sense of teacher-student conference, Murray (1985) suggests that the student and the teacher should jointly read the student's work rather than the teacher just making comments. Furthermore, the student should speak first, commenting on his or her perception, then the teacher responds to the student's comments, thus beginning a dialogue which continues as the student responds to the teacher. Murray also emphasises that conferences should focus on one or two major issues central to the student.

Graves (cited by Turbill, 1983, p. 21) says:

At the core of the conference is a teacher asking a child to teach her about the subject. The aim is to foster a bursting desire to inform. So, the teacher never implies a greater knowledge of this topic than the child possesses, nor treats the child as an inferior learner. We are in the business of helping children to value what they know. Ideally, the poorer the writing, the greater interest the teacher will show in it - or rather in what it might become.

The importance of conference done by children both with their peers and their teachers or other adults, is also stated by the Education Department of Western Australia, 1994b. It reads:

children need time to interact with peers and as many adults as possible. It is from this interaction that they will reassess their theories and refine their skills as they move towards more competent, correct and satisfying writing. The type of interaction teachers have with children is critical (1994b, p. 58).

Calkins (1991), based on her experience in conferencing with Donald Murray, realises that the conferences were beneficial for her to make her a writer, and she concludes that it is best when the teacher does conference with children, s/he starts with researching, which may involve reading the draft and hearing the children's reading of the draft, and then asking questions, not little questions to show the teacher's interest in the children's topic, but big questions about their experience and intentions and problems and discoveries in writing the draft and writing in general. Then the teacher should think what is the one thing that might make the biggest difference to the child she/he is conferencing with. And finally, there would be teaching - teaching in a way that commands attention and makes a world of difference. The conference, in general, should be characterised by the teacher saying one thing simply and clearly, beginning with what she/he notices, what she/he sees, and then makes a suggestion based on that, saying, for example: "One thing you might try is"

Calkins (1986, p. 15) says that only through the conference, in which the teacher can observe what works and what does not work for each child as a writer, can the teacher assist best, by interacting with students so that they can interact with their writing, not just for five minutes but for a lifetime.

Turbill (1983) further says that the conference is the great advantage of individualised learning over generalised teaching, and quotes Sue Hutchins (a teacher applying the process-conference approach to teaching writing), who says,

The conference is an excellent way of getting to know and understand each child. Questions such as why did you write that? or what makes you say this? delve into the reasoning and ideas

behind what might have been a trivial tale. ... The conference is the key to better writing and better teaching (1983, p. 21).

It is also through the conference, as Parry and Hornsby (1985) say, that the child discovers, clarifies, and refines what he or she wants to express, and then comes to grips with the actual process being used and learns his or her areas of strengths and weaknesses. In addition, Gordon (1986) reports that as the process-conference approach demands sharing, peer group discussion and constructive criticism, talk or conference which may take place between, during and after drafts is very important. She says:

by conferencing with other students and teachers, students improve their reading, clarify their own ideas and expression, and extend their ideas, vocabularies and expression skills. Students of varying abilities and interests thus consciously extend each other. The product, the published writing, being highly individual, is most appropriately evaluated on its own terms rather than in any form of competitive assessment. ... Even students with minimal literacy can produce meaningful and attractive publications ... (1986, p. 24).

Emmit & Pollock (1991) mention about the importance of the conference as hearing others' responses to our thoughts forces us to modify, change, and extend our thinking as we take on board the ideas of others. Conferences also allow children to articulate their ideas as well as to listen to others. Through the discussion process in the conference, they suggest, the richness of many ideas can be shared and the learning of many students can be enhanced.

Turbill (1982) and Sangirardi-Gray & Meltzer (1993) report the importance of peer conference, particularly in upper grades, when children are getting more reliant on their peers rather than adults. Furthermore, Sangirardi-Gray & Meltzer say that "peer conferences are important for two reasons: they build self-confidence and self-reliance in students writers and they help teachers with time management during writing sessions" (1993, p. 57).

There are several types of conferences, and they may range in time from a few seconds to ten or even fifteen minutes. These conferences which may be labeled as the roving

conference, the sharing conference, the group conference, or publications conference, can also be considered as brief discussions, and may occur before, during and after the writing.

During a conference with a child, the teacher is advised to provide support at the child's point of need, thus individualising the teaching/learning. When the teacher finds a child who does not know the spelling of a word, according to Turbill (1982), the teacher may help the child by showing her/him how to sound out the words, so the children will try to invent their spelling when finding the same problem. This will make them not too worry about spelling when they write the first draft. Sowers (1984, p. 39) reports: "Invented spelling gives young writers early power. Professional writers don't worry about correct spelling on the first draft and neither do inventive spellers."

In addition, Mc Donald (1991) suggests that when listening to children's writing during the conference, the teacher should remember two things: be positive, and be precise. The teacher's first comment should be a positive one, like "I like your beginning ...," "What a lot action you have in this story. I really like that." Furthermore, Turbill suggests that during the conference, children share and discuss their ideas about what they want to write, what they have written, and how they can improve their writing, and constructive criticism is given by the teacher to the novice writers" (1991, p. 30)

4. Publication - the principle purpose for writing

The essence of this tenet is actually finding readers, as the principal purpose underlying the writing process is not to produce writing, but reading, to publish a finished product for readers (Walshe, 1981). "Writing is a public act" (Graves, 1985b, p.159).

The readers for children's writing are not just the teacher, but also fellow students (whom Moffett, 1983 considers to be a natural audience) and various people beyond the community of the classroom, like parents, brothers, sisters.

Publication allows students to be motivated to write because they have readers interested in reading what they have to say, as it is the case with any writer that the most important influence on her/him is the audience - that is when there is a prospect of publication. As a consequence, the writing is not just something to be handed into the teacher to be marked, or for exercise purposes only, but something available to other people to read. In this case, Turbill states that "publication boosts the children's egos, raises their confidence as learners ... " (1982, p. 82). In addition, Walshe (1981) mentions that children discover a great deal of self motivation when they write for readers who they think will be interested or impressed by what they write.

The publication can be in a form of a published book, classroom display, letter, report, poster, postcard to make children proud of what they have done. It can also be read in front of the class, or shared with their friends. In doing so, the writing has now become public in a real sense. In terms of the audience, Britton *et al* (1975) categorise writing as: writing for *self*, *teacher*, *wide known audience*, and *unknown audience*.

In relation to publication, Murray (1982) says that writing is a shared product. Once the writing is produced, it is shared, and the sharing, particularly at the beginning should be done orally. He claims: "When the children read their papers aloud, they hear the voices of their classmates without the interference of mechanical problems, misspellings, and poor penmanship" (1982, p. 27).

Similarly, Education Department of Western Australia (1994b) mentions that in "sharing time" children are provided with opportunities to present finished work to an audience or to gauge audience reaction and receive constructive feedback to early drafts of writing, and teachers are provided with opportunities to observe levels of

understanding displayed by individual children and to plan follow-up activities when necessary to consolidate learning. It is further stated:

These sessions (sharing time) are highly motivating as children have a real purpose and audience for their productions. Children also learn the appropriate oral language skills involved in giving and receiving feedback. They become more tolerant and develop respect for the efforts of others. Sharing time encourages children to reflect upon, and share, each other's language work in a community of readers and writers (1994b, p. 15).

In terms of publication, Turbill (1982) and Graves (1983) suggest that not all drafts should be published in the sense of real publication, like display, or sending to the real audience, like letters, but only one out of, say, four. However, all drafts should be dated to record progress. "Publishing for the children runs about one piece published in each of four to five booklets" (Graves, 1983, p. 55).

When children's writing is published - sent to a real audience or displayed, publication, Turbill (1982) says, involves several things, including: attractive presentation through neat handwriting, correct spelling, helpful punctuation, good page layout, presentation to interested readers-immediately to the teacher and classmates, and later perhaps to other classes and parents.

In addition to the basic tenets discussed above, there is one more principle that Graves (1989b; 1994) has added to the process-conference approach. That is the emphasis of writing nonfiction, particularly for the intermediate grades. In this case, Graves suggests that children should be encouraged to write not only fiction, but also nonfiction in a broader range of genres. Graves (1989b, p. 33) says: "As they grow older, children will need to write more extensive nonfiction pieces because issues will arise in the classroom that require their use." Graves (1989b, p. 33-34) further points out that the genres of nonfiction that can be introduced to the children include the essay, the letter, directions, lists, formal and informal arguments, satire, humor, interviews, note taking, informal and formal reports. He states that these genres are best introduced to the children through the mini-lesson workshops. Moreover, the genres should be introduced not only within the context of classroom issues, but also

of events outside the classroom and the school. As a result, the children will see the relevance of all the genres and will see how these forms of writing can serve their own needs.

Graves (1989b) mentions that the teacher has to encourage children to experiment with a number of nonfiction forms as children's reading diet has also changed. Children's interest has now expanded into biography, historical fiction, information books and nonfiction books in areas of special interest.

With respect to the importance of nonfiction, Graves (1994, p. 313) mentions:

Nonfiction is an important genre for helping children and ourselves to know an area particularly well. In this sense, nonfiction is probably the most usable kind of writing for school and a lifetime of work. Sadly, children can complete their school careers and never experience the joy of really digging into information they wish to know well, of satisfying their curiosity about something that fascinates them. Until learners understand what it means to know something very well, they will settle too quickly for skimming the surface. And somehow we think that our splintered curricula can inspire the fascination about what it means to know.

Furthermore, Graves (1994) mentions poetry as another genre of writing that children in the process-conference writing classroom should experiment. Like nonfiction, poetry can be done by children within ten or fifteen minutes, and then the teacher responds to what the children have produced.

Several Conditions in The Process-Conference Writing Classroom

The writing classroom in which the process-conference approach is applied, according to Cambourne & Turbill (1987), should have several conditions, which include:

- immersion: teachers surround children with print - a wide variety of print - including the labels on the art and craft work around the room;
- demonstrations: teachers demonstrate how they write, how they spell, how they check punctuation, and demonstrate how drafts are written;
- responsibility: it is the children that take responsibility to make a decision on what topics they will write;

- expectations: teachers expect their children to have a go at spelling the words they don't know, to be able to choose their topics in writing. Teachers are also careful not to communicate that certain tasks are achievable by some children and not others. Teachers avoid grouping children in ability groups, but encourage cooperative learning in flexible groups;
- approximation: children are encouraged to "have a go", and are not expected to attempt to be perfect first time around;
- practice: children are given time and opportunity to write for purpose;
- response: mutual exchanges between experts and novices - children interact with both the teacher and friends about their writing, in such a way that the children can get feedback which is both supportive and instructive.

- **Criticisms of The Process-Conference Approach to Writing**

There are several criticisms of the process conference approach, stated by the critics, particularly those who advocate the genre approach (which will be discussed later in this chapter). The first criticism is related to the concept that children learn to write by writing, in the same way as they learn to speak, which, according to them (Rothery, 1986a; Walker, 1987; Collerson, 1989b; Cope & Kalantzis, 1993) has led children to write only narratives or recounts, because the closest genre of writing to speaking is the story. They also say that this has happened because the teacher in the process-conference approach does not teach writing explicitly and does not induct the students into the varieties of written language which are crucial to success in the education system. On this issue, Cope and Kalantzis (1993, p. 68) write:

Some genres, even though they are still characteristically written, are closer to the distinctive features of speech than others. A written persona recount, for example, can have features characteristically closer to speech than other forms of writing. This, incidentally, is why process writing, so long as it maintains its ideological commitments to the voice of the creative individual and to the basic similarity of oral and written language, will rarely take students beyond recount.

They further quote Vygotsky who argues that the development of writing does not repeat the developmental history of speaking. Even the minimal development of

writing requires the high level of abstraction. They say: "Inner speech is almost entirely predicative because the situation, the subject of thought, is always known to the thinker. Written speech, on the contrary, must explain the situation fully in order to be intelligible" (Cope & Kalantzis, 1993, p. 71).

Walker (1987), in reporting his observations in the process-writing classroom, points out that various steps of writing that culminate in publication, are encouraged to be done by the children only when they write stories. When the children are required to write in other content areas like social studies or science, the same steps do not appear to be expected.

In addition, Christie, Martin, & Rothery (1989) argue that teachers in the process approach do not teach their students about language, for the reason that the curriculum planning information that they have received has discouraged them from doing so.

Another criticism of the process-conference approach is related to the concept of free choice of topics. In this case, Kamler (1992), who analysed the writing of two children, a boy (Peter) and a girl (Zoe), who were taught writing under the process-conference approach, found that free choice of topics creates gender stereotypes and dominant social stereotypes and biases. Like Poynton, Romatowski & Trepanier-Street (quoted by Gilbert, 1993), Kamler found that girls and boys write about different things. Girls tended to attribute emotional states to their characters and more pro-social behaviours than male writers, and male writers frequently constructed characters who were verbally and physically aggressive. Girls tended to include descriptions and acted as a recipient of someone else's action, while boys wrote about action and story in which they acted upon the world. In some cases children write about sexist, racist or violent topics which are values not generally promoted in the classroom. Hence there is a tension between the teacher's values and the child's.

In terms of free choice of topics, Kamler (1992) further asserts that children are not free to express themselves in the process writing classroom. Children are directed by many constraints to make one set of choices over another. Even when teachers believe that they are giving children free choice, she says, "their discourse, the way they set up their classrooms, the dominant values of the culture, all operate as constraints which direct children's choices in particular directions, whether teachers are conscious of this occurring or not"(1992, p.105).

The third criticism of the process-conference approach is related to one of the stage in the process of writing that children have to pass through, that is "revision". In this case, the critics say that children cannot pass through stages as professional writers do, because although we treat them as real authors, they can not act as real authors, due to their incapability, particularly in revising. In reporting results of studies of editing and revision, Bartlett (1982) writes that children, unlike real authors, do not know how to make their writing better. Although they know they have a problem, they do not know how to solve it.

Based on her study, Bartlett (1982) concludes that it is difficult for children to revise their writing. She claims: "When students revise at all, they generally focus on changes at the level of individual words or phrases. ... More important, perhaps, is the finding that revisions do not always result in appreciably better text" (1982, p. 346). She then quotes Bracewell, Bereiter and Scardamalia, who also found that there is no reliable differences in the quality of original and revised versions of essays produced by elementary and high school students.

Moreover, she claims that there are two components of revision processes: evaluation and correction, and these processes are carried out together. However, her finding was that children could do the first component of revision, that is evaluation or detection, but could not do the other, that is correction. This can be seen from the result when

children revised texts containing ambiguating information. 62 % of problems were detected by the children and of these, 95% were not successfully corrected.

The fourth criticism of the process approach is that the concept of authorship and free choice of topics advantages only a certain group of children, in this case, children from the upper middle class. The critics say that because children are free to choose their own topics children from the upper middle class, who are used to being read stories in a variety of genres and have already been introduced to writing in a variety of genres used in their families, will benefit and will be empowered much more than those from the working class/lower socio-economic groups who do not have the same literacy experiences as those from the upper-middle class. Martin, in Richardson (1991, p. 4) argues:

With its stress on ownership and voice, its preoccupation with children selecting their own topics, its reluctance to intervene positively and constructively during conferencing, and its complete mystification of what has to be learned for children to produce effective written products, it is currently promoting a situation in which only the brightest middle class children can possibly learn what is needed. Conferencing is used not to teach but to obscure. This kind of refusal to teach helps reinforce the success of ruling-class children in education; through an insidious benevolence other children are supportively encouraged to fail.

In addition, Gilbert contends:

Far from regarding authorship as a novel and reasonably effective way of encouraging children to write..., I am now concerned about the way this term, ... may operate to the disadvantage of many children by perpetuating romantic notions of writing as creative and individual expression. I am concerned that concepts like authoring might obscure the fact that school writing is about the acquisition of specific cultural capital ... (1990, p. 56).

The fifth criticism of the process-conference approach is related to the concept of individualised, student-centered writing and the concept of authorship. The critics say that authorship ignores the fact that writing is also a social activity (Gilbert, 1990) and ignores the fact that the goal of literacy is always societal (Edelsky, 1994). Gilbert (1990) says that the use of the concept of authorship may operate to disenfranchise many children from any real understanding of the social, learned nature of writing and to deny them access to the obvious power of cultural literacy. In addition, she says, such terms serve to authorise some children's disadvantage because they construct an

image of language learning which is “personal, not learned; individual, not social, innate, not environmental” (1990, p. 56).

In relation to this, Gilbert & Rowe (1989) assert that literacy classrooms play an important role in the construction of children’s understandings of written language practices, their understandings of how people write, and what it means to be a writer. They further claim that when children enter into the domains of literacy learning, they are learning much more than to read and to write. “To learn to read and to write is also to learn about social and cultural practices, and part of such practices is to learn what it means to be a girl/woman or a boy/man in contemporary society. ... and the school’s role is obviously crucial”(Gilbert & Rowe, 1989, p.1).

Gilbert (1990) counters that the individualised and student-centred approach is contradictory to the fact that writing is about constructing from within an available signifying system and like reading is learned cultural practice. In emphasising the personal aspects or voice, and suggesting to children that they are authors, just like real authors, teachers and students are being misled into seeing writing as something which belongs to the child and can not be tampered with by the teacher. In the end the teacher is left with very little to say about the child’s efforts and there is precious little she can do to improve on poor writing.

- **The Genre-Based Approach**

Genres are defined as social processes which are goal-oriented and manifested differently in different cultures, as people in different cultures use particular genres , in specific ways, to realise their different social purposes (New South Wales Department of Education, 1990a,d). Genres are also socially constructed conventions of writing; they are the accepted conventions for doing things, connected with writers’ purposes” (Barton, 1994, p. 55).

This approach to the teaching of writing is based on the idea that language is a social activity, and it is through language that people achieve particular social goals, like to inform, to serve, to complain and to attract attention, among other things (New South Wales Department of Education, 1990a,d). So, according to the genre-theory, in order to get equitable social access and different kinds of social power, students need to be taught different social purposes of language in different contexts to predictable patterns of discourse (Cope & Kalantzis, 1993).

Unlike in the process-conference approach, where the teaching comes later after the teacher observes what the students do, or what works and what does not work for each child, in the genre approach, explicit teaching comes first, and then the children follow what the teacher does and tells them to do. In this case, children learn genres by some form of copying, and the process of teaching and learning under the genre approach can be seen based on the curriculum cycle used in the approach, which will be described as follows.

There are three major phases in the curriculum cycle of a genre-approach to teaching writing (New South Wales Department of Education, 1990a,b,c,d). These are:

- phase one: modelling of text 'in context';
- phase two: joint negotiation of a new text; and
- phase three: independent construction of text.

What follows is the discussion of activities that might be included in each phase.

1. Modelling

In this modelling phase, the teacher introduces a particular genre to the children as a starting point which can provide the occasion for information sharing between teacher and students-a shared context for the other modelling activities which will follow.

In this phase, the teacher explains a number of things, such as the purpose of a particular genre, the form that particular genre takes, the grammatical pattern peculiar to that genre.

Next, a number of model texts related to the genre are introduced - ones that show how the same field can be treated in different ways. These model texts can be used to draw out the significant features of the genre: those things which make a report a report, or a discussion a discussion and not a procedure. Then, social purpose, text structure and language features of the genre are also investigated (Calaghan, Knapp & Noble, 1993).

Activities that are involved in this phase are, among others: listening to, reading, discussing and interacting with a particular genre. When teaching the procedure genre, for example, recipes or car instruction manuals may be studied. These may be presented on the board, as an overhead transparency or in some other way which enables ideas to be shared.

2. The joint-writing phase

In this phase, the teacher and children write a text together. The board or an overhead transparency is used as the teacher guides and helps to organise ideas supplied by the children. This phase may involve questioning, rewording, summarising, prompting and teacher's acting as a consultant, from which the children are expected to gain the confidence and knowledge to help them write independently (Weightman, 1991).

According to New South Wales Department of Education (1990b,c) in this phase of the curriculum cycle, the teacher is still a guide but the students enter into more active participation in learning to write a particular genre. This phase includes two distinct stages:

- a. Preparation for joint-writing of a text in the genre;
- b. Actual co-writing of a new text (joint construction).

In stage one of the joint negotiation of text, the students make decisions about how they are going to prepare for jointly constructing a new text - whether through

innovating on well-known, say, narratives or building new narratives. They may need to talk together, retell a story, read some other stories and write a plan for their group text.

In stage two of the joint-negotiation of text, the teacher (or any competent other), acts as a scribe for the class group and shapes the students' contributions into a text which approximates to a particular genre under focus.

At the end of this phase, the teacher needs to assess the students in order to make decisions about what kind of activity to move to next. Some students may need more assistance with modelling activities and some may be ready to move onto the next phase-independent construction of a story.

3. The independent writing phase

There are five identifiable stages to this phase of the cycle:

- stage 1: preparation for independent construction of text in a particular genre;
- stage 2: individual writing in the genre;
- stage 3: consultation with teacher and peer conferencing about individual writing efforts;
- stage 4: critical evaluation of writing efforts-including editing and publishing;
- stage 5: creative exploitation of the genre and its possibilities;

It is in this phase that children are given the chance to write individually. While they may have a choice of topic, the writing must be in the same genre as the jointly written text. This phase involves gathering information, drafting and revising writing and consulting with teacher or peers when necessary.

When finished, the work will be published, and the form of publishing will vary according to the genre chosen. For instance, a unit on narratives might result in a class

anthology, while a unit on expositions might result in a number of letters to the editor of the local newspaper arguing for more equipment in the local park.

Through this three-stage process, the advocates of this approach believe that children increasingly gain control over a genre as they develop their knowledge of its purpose, form and grammar and learn how to organise and present that knowledge in written form. In addition, if students have been taught how a particular genre is constructed, what its purpose is, what stages they need to move through in constructing it, and the kinds of language which distinguish this genre from others, they will be far better equipped to handle writing on their own.

- **Criticisms of The Genre-Based Approach**

One of the criticisms of the genre-based approach to teaching writing comes from Calaghan *et al* (1993) who practised this approach for the Disadvantaged School Program in Sydney. They conclude that there are several problems that need to be addressed to ensure the ongoing development of this approach and its usefulness and practicality in the classroom. These problems range from the limitations of the conceptual model to the practical issues of turning good ideas into good practice.

The first and most general problem is the conceptualisation of the curriculum genre as a cycle. There is some concern that while a three dimensional spiral may be theoretically pleasing, its complexity might be of little benefit to teachers, who basically want a simple, workable model. Within the one genre, students can work through the sequence of the curriculum genre a number of times to gain even greater control of the genre, to explore increasingly complex language features, and to explore increasingly complex field issues or more sophisticated content. The degrees of complexity within singular genres and their requisite language features, however, may not be sufficient to cover all the knowledge demands of the unit content.

Another criticism is that the genre approach, with the teacher scribing, has a potential model of reproduction pedagogy. This can be seen, according to Calaghan *et al* (1993), that the independent writing of the children who have participated in the joint negotiation stage often showed monotonous similarities to the one constructed in the joint-negotiation stage by the whole class.

In relation to the way children learn a variety of genres by copying, as stated by Cope & Kalantzis (1993), Hall & Robinson (1994) counter that nothing can be learned by the children about authorship, and nothing can be learned by the teacher about the children when children learn to write by copying. They argue:

When a child's introduction to writing is copying, ... then nothing is being learned by the child about authorship, ... All the teacher can say about the piece of writing is whether it has been written neatly. There is nothing more to be learned about the child as a writer. Although it looks like a perfect piece of writing, it is in fact a perfect piece of nothing. By imposing upon a child a process of simply copying, the child's ability to assert power and control over its own learning is reduced to controlling the craft of copying shapes (1994, p. 123-124).

From the literature review, it is clear that there are a lot of authorities who highly value the process-conference approach to writing, but there are also educators who have strong reservations about the approach. This is why, it was felt to be valuable to research the way this approach is implemented in some Victorian schools. As this is an approach that could be introduced into the Indonesian education system, it is important to ensure that any recommendations as to its adoption, are well founded in research findings.

Chapter 3

Research Method

The study

This study explored four teachers' beliefs and understandings about the process-conference approach to teaching writing, their beliefs about the criticisms made of the process-conference approach, and how they applied the basic tenets of the approach.

Based on my classroom visits conducted in semester 2, 1995, two schools were observed using the process-conference approach to teaching writing. The encouraging results of this method of teaching writing, warranted closer examination, to discover how the teachers used the approach. As I want to introduce changes into the teaching of writing in Indonesia, it was of great importance that I researched exemplary writing programs of the process-conference approach.

To enable an in-depth examination of such programs, it was decided to limit the project to teachers of a grade 1, 3, and 5. Grade 1 was chosen because it is in this grade that children are often formally introduced to writing. Grade 3 and 5 were chosen to note differences in applying the basic tenets of the approach to older children and to note the children's development in writing ability after they have been exposed to this approach for a number of years.

Purposes of the study

This study was aimed at:

1. finding out the teachers' beliefs and understandings about the process-approach;
2. finding out the teachers' beliefs concerning the criticisms made of the process-conference approach;

3. exploring how the teachers applied the basic tenets of the process-conference approach.

The research was also to be conducted as a means to evaluate the suitability of the process-conference approach to writing and to ascertain the value of introducing such as an approach to the Indonesian Educational System.

Research questions

The research examined the following questions:

1. What are the teachers' beliefs and understandings about the process-conference approach to teaching writing?
2. What are the teachers' beliefs concerning the criticisms made of the process-conference approach?
3. How do the teachers apply the basic tenets of the process-conference approach?

Research method

To gain the data to answer the questions formulated in this research, a case study approach was employed. A case study approach was chosen for several reasons. First of all, case study is defined as "a study of a single case or bounded system, whether simple and specific, ... or abstract and complex" (Stake, 1985, p. 278). Case study designs "can range from small projects carried out by a single researcher ... on a self-funded basis to larger and most costly projects carried out by a team of researchers, occasionally over a period of up to fifteen years. The number of cases studied can range from one to hundreds ..." (Hakim, 1987, p.73).

As it is defined, a case study approach allowed for the intensive study of a small number of classroom. However, the small scale research conducted under case study design, does not mean that the research is superficial. A case study allowed for in-depth study or "down to earth" study (Cohen & Manion, 1985). With the small scale of

the study, a case study enables in-depth information to be obtained. Ary, Jacobs & Razavieh (1972, p. 87) point out that “the greatest advantage of a case study is the possibility of depth, in that it attempts to understand the whole subjects or participants in the totality of environment. Not only their present actions, their past, ... their emotions, their thoughts can be probed.” Cohen & Manion (1985, p. 146) write that “case study data, ... is strong in reality, ... because case studies are down to earth and attention holding” Hakim (1987, p. 61) mention that “a case study can provide a richly detailed portrait of a particular social phenomenon.” In addition, Connole (1993, p. 64) says: “the essential feature of a case study is the level of depth it can offer in researching all illustrative example of some phenomenon.”

Another reason for selecting this methodology was that case studies are typically based on two or more methods of data collection. This use of multiple sources of data, as Hakim (1987, p. 63) says, “allows case studies to present more rounded and complete accounts of the social issues and processes. The use of multiple sources of evidence makes the case study one of the most powerful research designs.” Moreover, Connole (1993, p. 59) says that “case study uses an in-depth study of a single or restricted number of cases using a variety of data-gathering methods.”

This use of multiple data-gathering methods suited my research as, based on the rationale mentioned earlier, it is clear that the information I needed would be best gained by interviewing teachers and observing what is conducted by the teachers and the students in the writing classrooms.

The description of the setting of the research, the participants and data-gathering techniques will be described as follows.

- **Setting**

The research took place at two Victorian primary schools. The reason for choosing these two schools was that, based on my classroom visits and conversations with some

teachers in the two schools, I could tell that these schools used the process-conference approach to writing, and that the results were of interest.

Furthermore, during my visit to these schools I was impressed with the students' writing ability and the teachers' knowledge about the theory that they applied in the classroom. I was also impressed with the fact that the teachers that I talked to during my visit to these schools were really committed to the theory and they tried to do their best to optimise their students' achievement in writing. It was of great importance that I observed exemplary examples of the writing classroom, which could be applied later in Indonesia.

- **Participants**

The participants of this research were teachers and students in grade 1 (two teachers from two schools, who will be called Teacher A1 and A2), a teacher of grade 3/4 (Teacher B) and a teacher of grade 5/6 (Teacher C). These three grade levels were chosen to determine how the process approach was applied in these three different levels. Moreover, the three grade levels were chosen to find out whether or not children's writing ability was increasing and whether they gained competence in writing after they had mastered the writing conventions and had been taught writing under the process approach for about three or five years.

- **Data collection techniques**

Two data collection techniques were employed in this research. These were interviews of the classroom teachers and participant observation of the classes.

- a. Interview

Interview has been defined as "a two-person conversation initiated by the interviewer for the specific purpose of obtaining research-relevant information, and focused ... on content specified by the research objectives of systematic description, prediction, or explanation" (Cohen & Manion, 1980, p. 241). Cohen & Manion further state that as a

data collection technique, interview allows for greater depth than is the case with other methods of data collection techniques, as it “provides access to what is inside a person’s head, (it) makes it possible to measure what a person knows (knowledge and information), what a person likes or dislikes (values and preferences), and what a person thinks (attitudes and beliefs)” (1980, p. 242).

Cohen and Manion also quote Kitwood (1977), who mentions the benefits of interview, which, among other things, is of pure information transfer, and writes: “if the interviewer does his job well (establishes rapport, asks questions in an acceptable manner, etc.), and if the respondent is sincere and well-motivated, accurate data may be obtained” (1980, p.244).

Based on the above description about interview, the interview was clearly the most appropriate data collection technique in this research to gain information concerning the teachers’ beliefs and understandings about the process-conference approach, and the teachers’ beliefs concerning the criticisms made of the approach.

The type of interview that I employed was a *guided interview*. The questions in the interview had been trialled with several teachers for suggestions and advice particularly regarding whether the questions were ambiguous, vague or confusing. Corrections were then made to make some questions clearer. A guided interview was chosen because this allowed for more information needed about the topic, while still giving the participants freedom of responses. Field & Morse put it:

A guided interview is used when information is required about a topic, when the structure of the topic is known, but the answer can not be anticipated. It is useful because this technique ensures that the researcher will obtain all information required (without forgetting a question), while at the same time permitting the informant freedom of responses and description to illustrate concepts (1985, p. 67).

The questions asked in the interview included the following:

1) *Questions to gain data about the teachers' beliefs and understandings about the process-conference approach (question 1-4 were developed from the questionnaire used by Bright, 1995)*

- a) How many years of teaching experience have you got? in what grade levels?
- b) If you are asked to characterise your writing program, what would you say? What would you emphasise?
- c) What are your chief goals in helping children to write?
- d) What kind of attitude would you want your children to have about writing?
- e) In general, what do you think are the strengths of the process approach?

2) *Questions to gain data about the teachers' beliefs concerning the criticisms made of the process-approach.*

- a) In the process approach, where children are allowed to write with the topic from their own, do you find your children write only stories with the same topic over and over again?
- b) Do you also find that free choice of topics creates children who write gender stereotypes and dominant social stereotypes and biases?
- c) During the process of writing, particularly in the revising stage, are your children able to revise and improve their writing?
- d) Do you also think that the process approach only advantages a certain group of children? Do you find some children who do not succeed in their learning to write?
- e) Do you find that the individualised program, like in the process approach, ignores the fact that writing is also a social activity?

All interviews, were tape recorded, to enable in-depth analysis of verbatim statements from the participants.

b. Participant observation (classroom observation)

Observation, according to Hopkins "is a natural part of any interaction process involving humans" (1980, p. 44). "Observation is used in the more usual sense: one or

more persons observe what is occurring in some real life situation, and they classify and record pertinent happenings according to some scheme” (Hapman, 1968, p. 58). Hapman further says that “observational methods furnish the primary means by which information on what is actually happening in a situation is obtained. Since it is often essential to have this information, observational methods are important in educational research” (1968, p. 58).

The reason for choosing classroom observation as one of data-gathering techniques is that, like other education researchers “who are concerned with process and product” (Hapman, 1968), this study was also concerned with the *process*, in this case the process of writing, what was happening in the classroom during writing sessions, what the teacher and students did, as well as *products*, which were the results of what happened in the classroom on the students’ writing ability.

During the classroom observation, notes were taken of everything which was specifically related to the questions formulated in this research. Hopkins writes, that in observation, “attention must be given to sorting out pertinent actions of an individual or group from those actions which have no bearing on the questions being studied” (1980, p. 51).

The observations focused on what the students and teachers did in every step of the writing process, including *pre-writing*, *writing*, and *post writing* stages, and everything related to the basic tenets of the process-conference approach, particularly including *free choice of topics*, *daily writing time*, *the conference*, and *publication*. The observation also focused on looking at whether or not the criticisms of the process-conference approach, as stated by the critics could be substantiated. The criticisms that I looked at were:

1. Process writing comes to be mainly story writing.
2. Free choice of topics creates gender stereotypes and dominant social stereotypes and biases.

3. In the stage of revising, children can not revise their writing on their own.
4. The process approach advantages only a certain group of children.
5. Ownership and individualised writing program ignore the fact that writing is also a social activity.

Because these two schools were used to having visitors in the classrooms, the presence of the researcher did not distract the children's concentration. What surprised me, and at the same time made me very happy being in the classrooms, was that all the teachers whose classrooms I observed allowed me the freedom to move around the class, to look at the children's writing, to talk to the children, and to conduct conferences with the children. The children had been asked to conference with me and read their writing to me, as if I had been their class teacher. Therefore, I became a participant observer, and this really helped me to gain a feeling for and a clear understanding of what happened, and what the teachers and the children did in the writing classroom. Taft (1989, p. 3.47) puts participant observation this way:

... direct experience of the researchers to be involved in the normal activities of the group provides the researchers with tacit knowledge which helps them to understand the significance to the group members of their own behaviour ... and enables them to integrate their observations about that behaviour with information obtained from other sources such as interviews ... and documentary material.

There were three observations of the grades 1 and 5/6 and four observations of the grade 3/4. Immediately after each classroom observation, a journal was written, recording the researcher's observations, feelings, reactions, and questions. This was done to promote the validity of the research, as Lofland (1971) suggests "record the notes as quickly as possible after observations, since the quantity of information is very slight over a short period of time but accelerates quickly as more time passes" (quoted by Cohen & Manion, 1980, p. 105).

c. Additional sources of information

Additional data collected in conjunction with this study included informal student interviews and samples of the students' writing. Of that additional data, only

information gathered from two student interviews and ten samples of student work was used in this research paper.

Procedure for analysing data

When all the data-collecting techniques had been used and all the data needed obtained, a *triangulation* was used, to make a contrast and a comparison of the information obtained, and then the data was interpreted. A *thematic analysis* was then developed for analysing the data. In this case, I categorised the data into themes that had become the focus of my research. The data from interviews were categorised into that of the teachers' beliefs and understandings about the process-conference approach and of the teachers' beliefs concerning the criticisms made of the approach.

The data from the classroom observations was categorised according to the basic tenets of the process-conference approach, including:

1. Writing is treated as a process.
2. Generally free choice of topics.
3. Daily writing time.
4. The conference.
5. Publication.

Afterwards, the interpretation of the data was confirmed with the teachers, to ensure that any interpretation was correct, as Taft says: "If necessary, the interpretation can be negotiated with the participants so that the final report is more likely to represent the situation as they see it (1989, p. 63). This confirmation was also conducted to obtain feedback and comments from the teachers to ensure the validity of the final report.

Chapter 4

Results

In this chapter, the data obtained from interviews and classroom observations are described and presented, according to the research questions and analysis procedure formulated in chapter 3. The data are divided into three sections, namely:

- Teachers' beliefs and understandings about the process-conference approach, gained from the interviews;
- Teachers' beliefs concerning the criticisms made of the process approach, gained from the interviews;
- Application of the basic tenets of the process approach, based on data gained from the classroom observations.

Teachers' beliefs and understandings about the process-conference approach

In this section, the responses from each teacher to the questions in the interview are presented and summarised. The complete responses of each teacher are presented in Appendix.

Teacher A1

Teacher A1 has been teaching for 12 years, primarily teaching lower primary, grades prep to two. In characterising her writing program, teacher A1 said that her writing program was changing. She said:

At this grade level [grade 1], I used to only emphasise writing diaries, recounting, say we go on an excursion, retelling. But now, I realise that younger children are just as capable of doing more difficult things, like writing a weather report, instructions, letters, and we're trying some different skills. Now I have always had the belief that young children can do that if you demonstrate how you do it, you take them step by step (Appendix, p. 112).

Her chief goal in helping children to write was letting the children have more confidence in themselves, to have a go, to try, to give them the opportunity and help develop the children's confidence in writing, to be positive about writing, enjoy

writing, be willing to have a try, not be afraid to make mistakes because, as she tried to explain to the children, we learn through mistakes.

Related to the strengths of the process-conference approach, teacher A1 mentioned several points.

1. The process-conference approach is more organised, in that we do not teach a whole group at once, as the days of teaching a whole group at once are gone. This is a more interesting way of teaching writing because the children can go off and write what they were interested in, not just what the teacher wants them to write about.
2. Demonstration helps children talk through thought processes and learn how to organise their thoughts. She said: "if we show them, we help children who are good at listening, as well as watching" (Appendix, p. 113).
3. Publication makes the children realise that they write for a real purpose, and when they write for a real purpose (for example writing a letter to their grandmother), they write better, because they have the reason to do it, not because the teacher teaches them.
4. Daily writing time gives children a lot of opportunities to write. Writing is like reading. If they don't write often, or read often, they can't learn to read or write. The more they read, the better they become readers, and the more they write, the better they become writers. In the classroom, particularly in integrated study time, writing does not happen just in writing session. In science, for example, they have to write a little report on what they have learnt.

Teacher A2

Teacher A2 has been teaching for 20 years, teaching in all grade levels except for grade 3, including many years in grade 1.

Teacher A2 characterised her writing program as a whole language program, emphasising it as a whole, not emphasising any of the particular areas of language, covering everyone of them, using and finding the children's strengths and helping them build on those.

Her chief goals in helping children to write were to give the children a lot of experience in every sort of writing, such as a story writing that we're used to doing, in all different areas of writing, and just to help them express themselves. She also wanted the children to enjoy what they were doing. She said: "If they're enjoying what they're doing, they're enjoying learning, they will learn a lot more than if they are unhappy" (Appendix, p. 114).

With respect to the strengths of the process-conference approach, Teacher A2 thought that in an individualised program it is possible to cater for every child at his/her level and we could work in an easy way to manage catering for individual children. She said: "If the teacher teaches just in one group, it doesn't cater for all children because there are some children who have gone further" (Appendix, p. 114). In addition, she mentioned several points, namely:

1. Publication, can show that she values the children's writing and that they write for a purpose and that children share ideas. Children love seeing their work.
2. Ownership, is a very important part of the approach, to make the children realise that they are doing writing by themselves. She said:

We have gone into a stage where we know we have some ownership of something. With ownership, we're more prepared to try a bit harder or work at a better level, because children feel very confident and they write more easily when they write about what they know, and they have ownership of their own writing, rather than someone else telling them all the time. On the contrary, when the topic is new, and the children do not know a lot about it, the children find it difficult to write (Appendix, p. 114).

3. In the conference, we can also show the children that we value their writing and they write for a purpose and they share ideas, as they talk about what they have written.

Teacher B

Teacher B has been teaching for 30 years, 12 years emergency teaching, in every grade level and every specialist area.

She characterised her writing program as a whole language writing program, focusing on writing with purpose, and encouraging children to have their opinions and to think about topics that were happening around them. She claimed: "We always start with the child-centered ideas-what they know about the topic, and we go from there. We also usually select the topic, but basically we start from the child" (Appendix, p. 114).

In helping children to write, her chief goal was to help the children express themselves and their ideas, to gain confidence in themselves and to know that they could write. Children with difficulty were helped to build up their confidence and skills. In addition, her goal was that the children were able to write confidently, to proofread their work, to recognise that they had some work which doesn't look right, to recognise that they should have full stops in some places, and commas in others.

With respect to the children's attitude towards writing, Teacher B wanted the children to enjoy their writing process, to enjoy putting their thoughts down on paper and to be really pleased with their final product.

In relation to the strengths of the process approach, Teacher B said that the process approach allowed flexibility for the children to write based on their ability. She said:

I find that I am not as rigid as I was. It's fine when children produce a short piece of writing, but they are happy with that, and they feel they've got their message across. So, the children can produce something of their own. Furthermore, the children have a purpose for what they're doing, it makes sense for them, and the children enjoy writing because writing has meant something to them. They write because they want to do it, or they want to find out something which is interest to them (Appendix, p. 116).

However, she further stated:

We have got to be very careful that the process writing approach by itself is not to be all and end all. You still have to have your spelling and your grammar. You still have got to monitor

what children are writing, how they are writing and what grammatical and spelling mistakes they have made (Appendix, p. 116).

In addition, she mentioned several strengths of the process-conference approach.

1. Brainstorming enables children to see how everyone's idea is accepted, nothing is wrong, nothing is unacceptable, and by giving the children a chance to write several times, children will know that there is a stage for making their writing better.
2. The conference allows the teacher to show the value of what the children have really done their very best, and we can give them courage to try. She also said:

By doing conference, we can also try to do justice for all, we learn from each other, we realise that we don't cover everything. Moreover, conferencing is important to help children who do not want to revise. When they read their piece, reading them aloud, they can actually hear where they have made mistakes, where they're leaving words, etc. (Appendix, p. 116).

3. Publication enables children to sort of have pride in their ability to produce their work. She said: "When they see finished product, they really do [have pride in their writing]. "Oh, I've done that. This is my work, I will get all that published" (Appendix, p. 116).

Teacher C

Teacher C has been teaching for 2 years, in grade 5/6. She characterised her writing program as a very child-centered program, giving the children many different sorts of styles of writing, different genres, and encouraging the children to do a lot of editing, on their own or with peers. She was involved in the process only to demonstrate how to write and to help the children with the final editing.

In relation to her chief goal in helping children to write, teacher C said: "My aim is to make the children not have fear in writing, so that they are happy to attempt things. When they look at their work, they'll improve it, and their clarity and presentation, in the long run are showing development as writers" (Appendix, p. 117). The attitudes that she wanted the children to have were to be willing to take risks, to try, to be happy to attempt things.

Like other teachers in this study, Teacher C mentioned the strengths of the process-conference approach, namely:

1. The process-conference approach enables children to develop individually, at their own pace, or at their own level. In addition, with expectations placed on them, they tend to bring to writing more than just their own experiences, more than just their own styles.
2. The conference has enormous benefits, in which children are not just reading aloud a piece of work, then correcting it. With the conference children have a chance to explain what they mean, to look into the meaning further, to clarify their ideas, and to have someone tutoring their work as well. Teacher C said: "I think it [the conference] is really beneficial" (Appendix, p. 117).
3. Brainstorming is also important. She said: "we need to use a variety of ways of brainstorming still, not only writing on the board. Brainstorming also needs to develop into categorising into certain areas according to the agreed purpose of writing" (Appendix, p. 118).
4. Children also love publishing their work. They love to see themselves as writers and publishers. When they've finished, sometimes they take their work around to other grades.

In short, Teacher C said: "Process writing is excellent, but we need time, to add time when the children need it, like teaching grammar when the children need it" (Appendix, p. 118).

Teachers' beliefs concerning the criticisms made of the process approach

As in the first section, responses from each teacher to the questions in the interview are presented and summarised. The complete responses of each teacher are presented in Appendix.

Teacher A1

In relation to the criticism that the process-conference approach comes to be mainly

story writing with the same topic over and over again, Teacher A1 said that the children in grade 1 did tend to write stories, but she did not think that she should be worried about this because it is stories that the children were most familiar with. She said:

I think in grade one they do [tend to write stories], because that's what they're familiar with. But I don't think in grade prep, one and two you should worry about it. I think you start introducing the types. Surely, if it happens in grade 5 or 6, I would be worried, but my feeling is in year 1 you are just trying to introduce them a different type of genre. But you still want them to do a lot of writing, so, let them write what they're comfortable with. In your guided sessions, like I did yesterday (referring to the session when she taught instruction), that's when you can have them try a different genre, but in their free session, let them try to write in the area that they feel comfortable with. My feeling is I'm trying to get them to be positive about writing (Appendix, p. 118).

Teacher A1 also believed that children in grade 1 did write gender stereotyped writing, but she said she did not think that she should be worried about it either.

With respect to the criticism that children can not revise their writing, Teacher A1 said:

In year 1, it is a very difficult thing. What I have shown what my children to do is to underline the word they were very unsure of. And then, when we conference, I show them how to write properly. Sometimes, I let other children comment, and they do it in a positive way. Probably when the comments come from us, the children will get hurt, but if it comes from the children, they don't take it, and I think probably coming from the children is easier (Appendix, p. 119).

In response to the criticism that the process approach advantages only a certain group of children, Teacher A1 believed that children who were doing well at school did better at this program. With the children who were struggling, she felt that she had to give them extra help, and to give them ideas on how to start stories, how to get their ideas in their heads, and how to organise their thoughts. In helping children to organise ideas, she mentioned:

One thing that I've given to my children is a story plan. They have to draw a picture of 'when they did something, who they did it with, when they went and what they did.' I find my poorest students benefit from this, because it helps organise what they are going to say, then they could use the pictures to write their stories. So, it is very useful (Appendix, p. 119).

She further said:

I suppose, dealing with individual children at what level they are, hopefully, in this way, no child will feel a failure. The children who are ready to go ahead, can comfortably go to the next step, and the children that are struggling, should be given help as they are ready to be helped (Appendix, p. 119).

Finally, to the criticism that the individualised program ignores the fact that writing is a social activity, Teacher A1 responded that children wrote not only individually, but also in groups, particularly in integrated study times. She said:

When we do integrated studies, we do group work, where the group has to write a report. So, writing happens all day, it is not just in writing sessions. For example, when we are doing science, I'll have the children write a report as a group (Appendix, p. 119).

Teacher A2

In answer to the criticism that the process approach comes to be mainly story writing, with the same topic over and over again, Teacher A2 commented that the children did write only stories at the beginning because they wrote what they were secure in, based on their experiences. However, she said that if we used activities and immersed them in enough activities, children would learn and develop from that. She further said:

... yes, at the start, they will tend to stick to the one topic they're confident in. So, you have to try to build their confidence to have a go at different areas and give them a variety of genres, and take a few risks. When you teach, for example, space, in science class, a lot of writings have been done, like a report writing, writing a report of science experiments (that we've planned to go into), factual writing, and list (Appendix, p. 120).

Related to the criticism that free choice of topics has caused children to produce gender stereotypical writings, Teacher A2 thought that the experiences were more stereotyped. In grade 1 she still found that girls were more interested in some areas than boys. Boys are more interested in playing football and sorts of things. She said:

You'll find it (gender stereotypes) in their writing, specially in early development when they are still recalling, recounting, reading, recording what they have experienced. As they move on, it becomes less apparent. But, I just think that boys and girls are different and they will be interested in different things and we do have to try to take away that stereotypes that is always around, but we still have to be aware of the fact that boys and girls are different and do have different interests (Appendix, p. 120).

To the criticism that children can not revise their writing and can not make their writing better, Teacher A2 responded that the children who were developed more, in year 1 level, were beginning to become aware of that editing and revising stage. Teacher A2 demonstrated how to revise in her demonstration, when she and the children revised, as a group. When she wrote, she would get the children to help her to

write and to revise. She asserted: "We find that the children at a high level are ready to do that at this stage in year one" (Appendix, p. 121).

Furthermore, pertaining to the criticism that the process approach advantages only a certain group of children, Teacher A2 commented that the ones who developed slowly did need something extra, such as giving them a program which is an intensive program, when children learnt to have a sort of built skills in categorising, and some others built up vocabularies. In doing so, Teacher A2 said: "the children who have a go can go further, and those who struggle can at least express their ideas, which is very-very good" (Appendix, p. 121).

Finally, in answer to the criticism that individualised program ignores the fact that writing is a social activity, Teacher A2 asserted that this depended on when the children wrote. Sometimes children wrote just for their pleasure, sometimes for others. She said:

What we're doing is that whenever they're doing writing, we are making sure that they are aware of why they are doing it. Sometimes it is a social thing for other people to write and to read. In addition you have to make it clear that the writing has the audience and purpose, and another time writing is just for their pleasure. So, it's dependent on when they are writing (Appendix, p. 121).

Teacher B

Unlike Teacher A1 and A2, Teacher B, in response to the criticism that the process approach comes to be mainly story writing, did not think that children in her class wrote only stories with the same topic over and over again. She said:

We must have some directive writing periods, with the broader writing program. Quite often that their choices are within the framework, looking at the theme we're doing at that particular time. Some children need more guidance than the others. If they are repeating the same things over and over again, we need to give them some different stimuli that are getting them to think something different. Basically, our topics are within the area that we are talking about. Sometimes free story writing, sometimes we give them a topic, let them express ideas but within the topic talked about (Appendix, p. 121-122).

In addition, to make the children write in different genres, Teacher B tried to present the children with a lot of models, nonfictions, showed them actual differences in

nonfiction books, presented them with a different kind of genre, newspaper articles, etc.

In relation to the criticism that free choice of topics creates children who write gender stereotypes, teacher B thought that this was valid. Boys tended to write about bloods, guns, and girls tended to write fantasy. So, she tried to change that, to channel them to another version by putting some limitations on the children's writing, like no killing, no blood, no shooting.

Teacher B did not believe in the criticism that children cannot revise. She said:

Some know better than others. Some struggle with it. Some of them don't like doing it. They finish their writing, and that's it. We just keep encouraging them to read through their work and to proofread it, to check all the spelling and punctuation, does it make sense? Do I like what I have written? Is it what I wanted to say? (Appendix, p. 122).

To help children with the difficulty in the spelling of a word or words, Teacher B tried to get them to look at the words and say over to them, what sounds the words have. In relation to this, Teacher B said: "If they go through that process, the learning process is much better" (Appendix, p. 122).

Moreover, Teacher B did not believe at all in the criticism that the process approach advantages only a certain group of children. She argued:

No, I have some children in my room now who have very limited vocabulary but they're still not afraid to put their thoughts down on paper. They'll have a go with the words that might be phonetically mistake, but they make sense of it. They're not afraid to make mistakes (Appendix, p. 122).

To the criticism that individualised writing program ignores the fact that writing is a social activity, Teacher B responded that she did a variety of things to prove that writing in the process approach was indeed a social activity. She commented:

We might have a period of silent writing, where it's important that children write down on paper. We might also have a group of children brainstorming, working together, helping and learning from each other, in a large or a small group. In addition, the fact that you get the children to present what they've written to each other, help each other, share their writing with each other, means that there is a place for social practice. It's social in that way (Appendix, p. 123)

Teacher C

Teacher C did not believe in the criticism that children in the process-conference approach writing classroom write only stories with the same topic over and over again. She asserted that there were a lot of things that she did. Sometimes she gave the children a topic, sometimes the children had a choice of two or three different pieces of writing. For example, in history, they might have to write a letter to someone living a hundred years ago, or they might have to write a review of the work they had been doing. They might get a chance, in that session, to write one of the choices that they got. Over the whole term or the whole year, the children had to attempt to write each style of writing.

With respect to the criticism that free choice of topics creates children who write gender stereotyped writings, teacher C believed that this happened, but only in some cases. She said: “yes, that’s still the case in some” (Appendix, p. 123). However, she further said:

We can get away with that by putting them into different contents, say, we’re writing something where it’s got two strong contents or characters for boys and girls. It’s always important that children have a different role models, and we have to give them models by choosing a story that’s not gendered bias (Appendix, p. 123-124).

In addition, teacher C did not believe in the criticism that children cannot revise and cannot make their writing better. She believed that children should be taught how to revise. Children had to be modelled how to revise and many strategies had to be demonstrated. Furthermore, she said “They (children) should be encouraged to use their thinking, like editing their own spelling, using peers to read through and to check their work as well, underlining things” (Appendix, p. 124).

Teacher C did not believe at all in the criticism that the process approach advantages only a certain group of children. She responded: “Some children perhaps are not up to a great level, but I don’t think that there would be any difference, no matter which process you’ve been using” (Appendix, p. 124).

Finally, Teacher C did not believe in the criticism that individualised writing program ignores the fact that writing is a social activity. In response to the criticism, she claimed:

I don't think so [that individualised writing program ignores the fact that writing is a social activity], because we do have a great chance of making a social writing when we're doing a demonstration, when the children are working with their peers, when they are having a conference, modelling to each other. When they have finished writing, they are reading their piece, or they are displaying it. Again, they're seeing each other's work, which in this sense is a social practice (Appendix, p. 124).

Application of the basic tenets of the process-conference approach

Of four classes that I observed, what actually happened in the classrooms during writing sessions was basically similar and what follows are the descriptions of the writing sessions in relation to the basic tenets of the process-conference approach.

Teacher A1

- **Writing as a process**

In the first session observed, the teacher introduced a new genre of writing to the children, which was instruction. The teacher began the class by saying: "Now, we are writing another type of writing, which is instruction, to help someone to do something." Then, there was a question and answer session between the teacher and children:

T: When you write an instruction, do you start with 'once upon a time', or 'one day'...?

C: No.....! "To help you with ...".

T: Great!

The teacher then discussed with the children what kinds of instructions they could write, such as how to make a cake, how to change a tyre, how to make a leaf necklace, etc. At this time, the teacher wrote all the ideas coming from the children on the board. Afterwards, the teacher and students decided to write an example of instruction,

with the title “How to make a leaf necklace” The teacher demonstrated how to write the instruction on the board. She wrote:

How to make a leaf necklace

1. Take eight leaves.
2. Cut them out.
3. Put the thread through the middle of the leaf.
4. Add four noodles between each leaf.
5. Tie a knot.

At this stage, the teacher also explained to the children that the sentences could be organised using the words *first*, *second*, and *third*, etc. In addition, she explained the characteristics of the instruction genre, like ‘the language in instruction should be simple, in order that people can easily understand what we write.’

Afterwards, the teacher passed on a lined paper to the children to write instructions on their own. Before the children wrote, the teacher asked them to decide the topic first and to brainstorm about what they wanted to write. She suggested that the children write the date and the title first, and she also gave some more possible options, such as how to make a kite, how to make a cake, etc.

When the children were writing, the teacher approached each child, asking what the child was up to or what she/he was going to write, and whether or not they had problems or difficulty. One of the interesting things I observed was a conference between the teacher and student who was writing “How to make a quilt”. The conference can be described as follows:

T: Do you know how to make a quilt?

S: No.

T: So, don't write ‘how to make a quilt’ if you do not know how to do that.

Do you know how to make a sandwich?

S: Yes.

T: Then, write how to make a sandwich, (the teacher questioned her on how indeed a sandwich is made).

From my observation, it really impressed me that almost all children could find a topic and write about it very quickly. Some children helped each other, for example, one child said to a friend next to him, who was having difficulty finding a topic: "Why don't you write a sand house? It's easy."

When approaching every child for the first time, the teacher did not worry too much about the mechanics of writing; the spelling; and punctuation. She did, but only to some children who already had written a bit. The first help she gave to the children concerned with the content and finding a topic which the children knew to get her/him to start writing.

The teacher was concerned about spelling only for the last draft. For example, in my second observation, when the children wrote the last draft of a letter to their grandmothers, the teacher conferenced with each child, and helped them with spelling, punctuation, and the other conventions of writing used in a letter, such as salutation, greetings, date, etc. For the final copy, the teacher encouraged the children to write the letter neatly and to make sure that all the spellings were correct in order that their grandmothers could read it easily.

After finishing their writing, the children drew a picture on their piece, then they came to the teacher, for a conference. Afterwards, their instruction was published, by reading it in front of the class. After each child read their piece, the teacher asked other children to give comments on her/his writing. In this case, I was impressed with the way the children gave comments on their friend's writing. They could give suggestions to each other, on how to make their writing better, particularly in the content. When one child finished reading his writing, about "How to make a book" (Figure 1), one of

the children said: "I reckon his writing is good." In addition, because the last sentence of the instruction was "Then, we draw words on it" one of his friends said, "I think you do not draw words, but write words."

Another child wrote "How to plant" (Figure 2) and the last sentence of the writing read: "Water it every morning and night" and one child said: "We don't usually water plants at night, just in the morning."

Figure 1

Translation:

How to make a book

1. Get some paper.
2. Staple it together.
3. Write our name.
4. Draw a picture.
5. Under the picture, draw some words.

~~M. T. R. L. G. K. V. G. Y.~~
How to make a book
1. get samim paper
2. staple it togit
3. ritet ur name
4. draw a picture
5. ~~under~~ ^{write} ur pictt draw some words

Figure 2

Translation:

How to plant

1. Get some seeds.
2. Plant it in the spot in a pot or in our garden.
3. Water it every morning and night.

Every time the child finished reading her/his instruction, the teacher asked the children whether the piece was easy to follow. She said “instructions are written to help others, so, it should be easy to follow.” In addition, when there were some mistakes in spelling, or punctuation, the teacher asked the children to rewrite it.

From my observation, I also noticed that the teacher always valued what the children had done, saying: “Excellent; Well done; I like that,” or, “I like ... when writing”

- **Free choice of topics**

This principle was not applied every time the children wrote. I noticed free choice of topics was allowed when the children were writing instructions, and when the children wrote in groups about the news that each child brought to the classroom. When the

children wrote a letter, free choice of topic was not applied. The teacher and the children decided to write a letter to their grandparents.

- **The conference**

Conferences were conducted by the teacher several times: during the writing session, for example the teacher helped the children to find a topic, in the post-writing session she had the children read their writing to her. The length of the conference was different for each child, depending on their needs. With those children who found difficulty, the teacher conducted longer conferences than with the other children. In the last conference, when the children were reading their work and the children felt confident that their writing was finished, the teacher helped each child with spelling, punctuation, and grammar, and then the teacher asked them to write a final copy. When the writing was to be displayed or sent to a real audience, the teacher asked the children to write neatly and all spelling and punctuation had to be correct.

- **Publication**

Publication was done in several ways. For example, instructions were just read in front of the classroom; the letters were sent to the children's grandparents; group writing was published in a big book displayed in the classroom.

In this case, I noticed that publication made the children proud of their work and gave them more self confidence in their piece, particularly when they received positive comments from their friends and teacher, and when the teacher showed her interest in their writing.

- **Daily writing time**

In this class, writing was done every day, not always individually, but also in groups. For a couple of days children might work on the same piece, as one piece of writing might take several days, with several drafts, until they were sure that they did not have

any mistakes in their writing, particularly when their writing would be published/ displayed or sent to a real audience.

Teacher A2

- **Writing as a process**

When I first observed this class, they were learning about space. The teacher read one story book on space, and discussed the content of the book. Then, the teacher demonstrated how to write about space on a big piece of paper on the board with the title 'The Space Race', which was based on the topic in science that they had learnt.

The teacher asked several questions like: What do you think the story will be about? Is this realistic thing or made up story? Then she wrote as follows:

Once there were two big, strong astronauts with two enormous rockets. They decided to race (through) space to the moon. They began at a very fast pace but soon they slowed down because without gravity they began to float through space. (While writing, the teacher kept asking about the ideas that the children might have, and she explained a little bit about space).

Then the teacher and children read what had been written on the paper. The teacher asked whether the writing could be made better, for example, she focused the word "they" in the sentence 'They began at' She changed it to "the race" and she asked the children if it sounded better. The teacher also explained about grammar, like the use of past tense - 'decided' and 'showed'; capitalisation and punctuation - a capital letter was used for the word 'They' in the sentence "They decided ..." because it was the beginning of the sentence.

In my second observation, the teacher did the same thing - demonstrating how to write a story about what she did during the weekend.

After the demonstration, the children were writing individually or in groups. Sometimes the class was divided into five groups. Although the topic was generated by the teacher, for example when they were writing about space, the children were encouraged to write only what they knew and what they had learned, and in the genre they wanted, such as a list, a report or a story.

For the first draft on the writing stage, the teacher encouraged the children not to be too concerned about spelling mistakes, and encouraged the children to use the words found around the classroom. In this class, I found one student who was quite a proficient writer, but he always wanted his spelling to be perfect for the first draft. The result was that he wrote slowly. When he asked the teacher how to spell a word, every time he had some confusion, the teacher said: "Don't worry too much about spelling, because this is a first draft."

At this stage, the teacher also did conference with each child. She always gave encouraging comments on and showed interest in what the children had produced, and encouraged the children to write more, for example, by asking for more detail in the children's writing.

The children were also encouraged to share their writing with their friends. With the children who had difficulty in spelling, the teacher helped them to sound out the words, and emphasised the letter-sound relationship.

After finishing their writing, the children drew a picture about what they had written, and then they read their piece to the teacher. The teacher gave comments, like "excellent, well done", or asked a question to encourage the children to include more details in their writing. The children might also make a circle in front of the classroom, and then one by one read their writing. The teacher and the other students gave comments on her/his piece of writing.

From my observations, I found that in this class there were some writers, who were already very proficient and who could write a lot very quickly. Their writings were outstanding for first graders (Figure 3 and 4). They still did make several spelling mistakes, but they were already starting to revise their pieces. For example, in figure 3, the writer changed the word "haas" into "has", "kwnow" into "know", "Wa" into "What" and tried to change the word "aron" into "around" (although in this case, the writer did not succeed to correct the spelling). In figure 4, the writer changed "holiday" into "weekend", "wet" into "went" and "goid" into "going".

Figure 3.

Translation:

What I Know about Space

Earth has people on it.
Saturn has a ring around it
Aliens are not real.
Jupiter has gas on it.
The moon is a planet.
Jupiter is a planet.

~~Wa~~ ~~What~~ ~~I~~ ~~know~~ ~~know~~ ^{14 May}
~~about~~ ~~space~~
* Earth ~~haas~~ has peaple on it
* Saturn ~~haas~~ has a ring ~~around~~ ^{around} it
* Alians are not real
* Jupiter ~~haas~~ has gas on it
* the moon is a planet
* Jupiter is a planet

Figure 4.

Translation:

On the weekend on Saturday at midnight I went to the airport to see my aunty and uncle because they were going to go to Malta and my uncle might be staying there forever and I saw an airplane go down. It was fantastic.

ON the ^{the} ~~holiday~~ weekend
ON Saturday at
Mide vite I went
to the are pote
to see my Aunty
and akel ~~to~~ because
they went going to
go to motor and
my Akel Mite be
saying these for
ever and I saw
it are a plane go down
was FANTASTIC

- **Free choice of topics**

The concept of free choice of topics was not applied all the time. When the children wrote in science on the topic "Space", all the children had to write the same topic. But, when the children wrote a story about what they did during the weekend, the topic was chosen by the children.

- **The conference**

Conferences were conducted several times with every child, at all stages of the writing process. The length of the conferences was based on the need of the children. With the children who had difficulty, the conference took longer. In the first conference when the children were working on their first draft, the teacher's main aim was to help the children find. The conference was also to be conducted between friends, particularly with those who were fairly proficient in writing.

- **Publication**

Publication, was done in several ways. The children's piece about "Space" was published by reading it in front of the classroom, and then the story was displayed in the classroom. I also noticed another piece that children had written - that was a story about a pet, was displayed on the notice board in the school.

- **Daily writing time**

Writing was done every day. This might be individually or in groups, and may be writing a story or the content areas (for example science).

Teacher B

- **Writing as a process**

I observed this class four times. In my first and second observations, the children were writing about Anzac Day, because it was the week when Anzac Day was commemorated. In my third observation the children were involved in a silent writing - writing a made-up story with the topic chosen by themselves, and in my fourth observation, the children were writing about the animals they had learned about at the Tooradin Marine Life Centre, which they visited the day before.

At the beginning of the session, discussion about the topic, and demonstration of the writing done by the teacher. Then the children wrote individually. Although the topic was generated by the teacher, for example when the children were writing about Anzac Day, the children were encouraged to write about what they knew.

When the children were writing, the teacher approached each child, particularly those who found it difficult to write because they did not know a lot about the topic. To help these children who had difficulty writing about Anzac Day, for example, the teacher gave them information, about Anzac Day, and then let them "have a go".

During the observations, I talked to some children and asked about their writing. The child who could write about Anzac day very quickly and whose piece was modelled in the class (Figure 5) said: "I know a bit about Anzac Day and I got information about it at home." I also asked another child, whether she found writing was easy for her, she said "writing is easy for me, but when I find a difficult word, it is difficult for me."

Figure 5.

This is what ANZAC day means to me. ANZAC day is the day that you need to have 1 minute silence. The war started because the king of Austria was shot. I think that all soldiers were badges to show that they fought in war. ANZAC stand for Australia New Zealand Army Corps. There were two wars they were called World War I and World War II. Yesterday we should have had 1 minute silence to remember the people who fought in war.

During the writing session, to help the children to solve the problem with spelling, the teacher encouraged the children to sound out the word, to ask friends, to consult a dictionary, or to use "Have a Go" sheet, which can be described as follows:

Have - A - Go!!!

Name:		
You try	See me for a clue	See me again

From my observations, in this grade, I noticed that the children were quite proficient at their writing, their mastery in spelling, and particularly their ability in revising. In general, they could already recognise the spelling, punctuation and grammar mistakes. When they did conference with their friends, or when they read their friends' piece, they could tell, for example, that a word was incorrectly spelled. In figure 6 the writer corrected the word "like" into "liked", the word "on" and "we" which were previously in lower letters into a capital letters as they were the beginning of a sentence. In figure 7, the writer was already able to insert information or additional ideas. The process of lining out can already be seen in this writing. For example the writer inserted the word "tank" and the expression "I learnt".

After finishing their piece, the children drew a picture about what they had written, then they read it to, or with the teacher. When the children made mistakes, the teacher did not point out the mistakes, instead, she wrote or said: "2 spelling mistakes" or "punctuation" or "grammar". The children then had to work to find out the mistakes and correct them.

Figure 6.

Tooradin Marine Life Centre!

On Tuesday the grade three/fours went to Tooradin Marine Life Centre. I learnt alot. I thought the aquarium was going to be like dolphins, sharks rays, fish and eels swimming around you. The main part that I looked about the aquarium was the rock pool. In the rock pool I liked to handle the animals. After the aquarium we went on the boat. On the boat Jack told us about a ~~luncheon~~ ~~Whales~~ ~~we were~~ ~~on the boat~~ ~~we saw~~ ~~some mangroves~~. The third activity we went into a ~~room~~ room. There were bones, shells and dead animals. We were allowed to handle them. We learnt how people caught whales in the older days. Next we went into another room. That room was mostly about pollution. The lady gave us some seaweed to tast. Danile Adams ate seven pieces. After that we went for a walk. Lots of people found hermit crabs. It was a fun day!!

Figure 7.

I noticed that children might write several drafts before their writing was published or displayed or submitted to the teacher. In this case, the teacher said that writing several drafts was really beneficial for the children as there were some students whose writing did not make sense in the first draft, but was much better in the second.

- **Free choice of topics**

Like the first two classes observed, in this class, children were not allowed free choice of topics every time they wrote. When the children wrote about Anzac Day, and animals they learnt about at Tooradin Marine life centre, the topic was assigned by the teacher. Only when writing a made-up story did the children choose the topic by

themselves. However, the children were always encouraged to write what they knew about the topic. This could be seen from the fact that two children who did not go to the Life Centre were not asked to write about anything the children learnt in the centre. They just wrote about animals they knew.

- **The conference**

Conferences in this class, like in other classes, were held several times, but the conference between peers was noticeably more frequent. The teacher also encouraged the children to hold conferences with other students first, and then with her. As the writing competence of the three graders were already good - in spelling, and the other conventions of writing, the children could help each other in these conferences.

In the initial conferences, when the children were writing a first draft, the teacher did not care too much about spelling, she worried only about the content, about the topic, by asking if there was something that they had not written, then letting them go further. Only in the revising and editing stages, the spelling, the grammar, as well as the content were emphasised.

- **Publication**

Publication was accomplished in several ways. Children's pieces about Anzac Day were read in front of the classroom, with comments from friends and the teacher, and the final copy was submitted to the teacher. Their piece on Tooradin Marine Life Centre was made into a book and displayed in the classroom. I also noticed that group work about current issues was displayed in the class.

- **Daily writing time**

Writing was practised every day, not only in the writing session, but also in other content areas, like social studies and science. In this case the teacher said that writing is involved in every subject, even in Mathematics.

Moreover, children did not only write individually, but also in groups, such as writing about their ideas concerning current issues based on newspaper articles, such as the Gun Law debate, (Figure 8). In each group, each had her/his own duty: as a recorder, as a timer, a leader and a reporter. They wrote on a big piece of paper, or in a flip book.

Figure 8.

~~Project~~ Work
Children under 12 should not have a gun.
People without a gun licence shouldn't have a gun.
People shouldn't kill people with other guns they should just kill animals to eat.
People shouldn't have guns they should just use guns in war.
If you shoot over ~~the~~ people you should go to jail forever.
The police should bring back the straight jacket.
People who shoot other people should die.
Adults shouldn't have guns unless they asked the police.
People shouldn't be able to use them guns.
Guns should be illegal.
I wish mental people shouldn't have guns.

⑫ If people die of being shot the person who shot the person should die.
⑬ If people don't have a gun licence in Victoria it's illegal.

Teacher C

- **Writing as a process**

When I first observed this class, they were writing a letter to NASA (National Aeronautics and Space Administration), because they previously learnt about science, related to space and NASA.

At the beginning of the lesson, the process of selecting topics, brainstorming was a common strategy when the teacher jotted down the ideas that might be asked by the children to NASA; the topics that children probably wanted to write, namely: satellites, meteors, universe, temperature, planets, aliens, solar system, Nebulas, Rockets, Comets, etc.

The children then were given ten minutes to write down ideas that they might want to write. At this stage the children were just required to write ideas, only in words, not necessarily in sentences.

Afterwards, the teacher demonstrated how to write a letter to NASA. The letter can be described as follows:

Address of the school.

Dear Sir/Madam, /Dear Scientists at NASA,

I am doing a project on space and I need some information on the solar system.

Then the teacher demonstrated to the children how to revise, such as, how to change the word “need” into a more appropriate word, for example “would like”. The teacher circled the word need and changed it into “would like”. The teacher also gave a possibility of changing the sentence into “... could you please send me...,” or of adding ideas, such as asking for more information on the “planets and the solar system”. Furthermore, the teacher explained about the conventions of a letter, such as indentation, the date, the closing part of the letter, and signature.

Afterwards, the children were required to write on their own, to anyone and about anything they wanted. When the children were writing the teacher walked around the class, conferring with each child. If a child's writing was particularly good, the teacher read it to the whole class, and then she let the child write more, or revise the piece. After finishing their work, the children were encouraged to conference and proofread with peers first, checking any mistakes they had made, such as spelling, punctuation, grammar, or capitalisation.

It was very interesting that in this class, the process of writing the children passed through was nearly the same as that of professional writers. The revision by the children in their writing was apparent. They knew that they made mistakes, or that their sentences could be made better, before other people saw the mistakes. The revision done, was not only cutting and changing, but also adding, lining out, inserting ideas, like in figure 9 and 10. In figure 9, the writer crossed out, and changed the word "before" into "when"; the word "it" into "we", and crossed out the word "because". In figure 10, the writer inserted the conjunction "that", crossed out the word "but" and corrected the lower letter "t" into a capital one in the word "There".

Figure 9.

12 September 2095

Dear Uncle Graeme,

We are right next to Saturn and ~~it~~ we will probably be here in a few minutes. ~~Before~~ When we got ~~into~~ Saturn we went around Saturn's ring system because we got pulled around in Saturn's gravitational pull. After a few of Saturn's days we actually got out of the mill. Did you know that Saturn can hold 700 Earths but its material is more than 7 times lighter than the Earth?

Sir Mr Graeme Dukelet
12 ~~Wick~~ street Seckman Cr
St Kilda 80025 DK
The Earth

from Lucy

Figure 10.

6 July 5001
Dear Jerry Sweet,

Venus is so hot. Dad Mum
loves it here so much ^{that} she wants to build a
house. There is a really bad heatwave it is
probably the heat from the lava lake. Mum said
you could come and visit us from Candice.
P.S Don't forget your sunscreen.

Mr. Jerry Sweet
11 Marshfield way
Curnville 3210
The Earth

Venus

In relation to the revision, the teacher encouraged the children not to “white out” when they revised. She encouraged them to line out, in order that she could see the process of the revision. In the conference, when the teacher saw the lining out, she put double or triple ticks on it. At this time, the teacher or children might also read the piece in front of the classroom, and asked for comments from other children.

When the children finished the final copy, the children sent the letter to NASA. The letter they made in the second observation was displayed in the classroom, in the form of a post card.

During the observations in this class, I was impressed that most children in this grade knew the conventions of writing; they made only one or two mistakes in their piece. Many children did not make even one single mistake, in spelling, grammar or punctuation. If they did make mistakes, they knew and corrected the mistakes, before anybody else saw it.

- **Free choice of topics**

Free choice of topics was permitted when the children wrote a letter to anyone and about anything they wanted. However, when the children wrote about planets or space, the topic was assigned by the teacher and related to the area they had previously studied.

- **The conference**

Conferences in this class were conducted several times, with each child. What was different from other classes in terms of the conference was that in this class, all children did conference with peers, and their writing was always proofread first among themselves, before it was read by the teacher. In the conference, when it was not a first draft, the teacher explained the conventions of writing, like punctuation, capital letters, etc. but only to those who needed it.

During the conference, when the children read their work, the teacher always valued what the children wrote, by giving the children compliments, like “Good, I like that sentence”, or, “ Oh, excellent, very neat writing”, etc. With those who needed help, the teacher did conference several times, but with those who were independent, she just conferenced once or twice.

- **Publication**

Publication was done in several ways, by reading it in front of the classroom, and sending to a real audience, like the letter to NASA, or by displaying it in the classroom in the form of a post card, like the piece related to planets. However, all children’s writings were published in the sense that they were read by an audience. In relation to this, the teacher said, that not all children’s pieces were published, in the sense of displaying or sending to a real audience. Sometimes they were just read, and finished, because if the children had to write a neat copy every time they wrote, they would get bored.

- **Daily writing time**

The children did write every day, in every subject of the curriculum. As children completed several drafts, in a couple of days, they might do the same piece, revising or editing what they had written previously.

Chapter 5

Discussion of Results

In this chapter, the data presented in chapter 4, will be discussed in relation to the research questions formulated in chapter 3.

The teachers' beliefs and understandings about the process-conference approach

The first research question concerned the teachers' beliefs and understandings about the process-conference approach. From the results reported in chapter 4, particularly from interviews, several points can be made in answer to that question.

It is apparent that all teachers involved in this study had a very strong belief and understanding about the process-conference approach. This is evident in the way their beliefs and understandings matched the principles and practices suggested by the main advocates of the approach as in the literature, and as discussed in chapter 2.

All teachers characterised their writing program with the features that were consistent with those mentioned by the advocates of the approach: Graves (1983); Walshe (1981); Murray (1982); Turbill (1982, 1983); Calkins (1986), such as: writing for real and meaningful purposes, starting with child-centered ideas, catering for every child with an individualised writing program, using, finding and build on the children's strengths, giving children a lot of opportunities to write, to edit by themselves or with peers and teaching at the point of need.

The strength of the belief in the process approach was clearly revealed by the teachers A1 and B (teachers in grade 1 and 3/4 respectively), who have taught for a long time (16 and 30 years), that the way they taught and their beliefs had changed greatly over the years. In previous years, Teacher A1 taught first graders only stories and recount. She now believes that children in grade 1 are capable of doing more than writing

stories, but also instructions, weather reports, letters, etc. While Teacher B mentioned that now she is not as rigid as she was, by which she means that now she is more flexible in teaching writing, giving children more freedom and varieties of genre in writing. She also accepts more in the way of approximations (Cambourne & Turbill, 1987) from the children, when teachers encourage children to "have a go", and do not expect children's attempts to be perfect the first time.

This result suggests that the change in belief among teachers has taken place, and now the teachers believe that children can be writers, and children can and do want to write. These ideas are similar to the ideas of Donald Graves (1983), who writes that children can write at the age of 5 or 6, of Harste *et al* (1984) who report that children can write long before they enter school, and of Elbow (quoted by Jensen, 1993) who states that young children can learn to write before they can read, and that writing is the gateway to literacy.

Teacher C (teacher in grade 5/6) said that she gave a lot of opportunities to children to write, to edit, by themselves or with peers. This is typical of children learning to write under the process-conference approach, when they are encouraged to write every day, and to complete several drafts. The children are also encouraged to hold conference with peers, in order to help each other to make their writing better. These practices are consistent with the ideas of Walshe (1981), Turbill (1982), and Graves (1983).

Another aspect showing the strength of the teachers' beliefs and understandings of the process-conference approach was the chief goal they mentioned in teaching writing. All teachers basically had the same goal in helping children to write, namely that of letting the children "have a go", encouraging children to express themselves in every genre of writing without fear, to be more self confident in themselves and happy to attempt things, to be able to write confidently, in order that they can develop as writers. These chief goals are in line with what is suggested by Graves (quoted by Turbill, 1982) and Cambourne & Turbill (1987) that teachers should always try to

encourage children to be self confident, to "have a go" and not to expect to be perfect first time around. The self confidence acquired by children is very important as when the children already have confidence in making topic choice in say, stories or recounts, they are more able to cope with the content subjects, where some prescription of subject matter is necessary.

The attitudes that the teachers wanted the children to have, also demonstrated the teachers' strong beliefs and understandings about the process-conference approach. All teachers wanted the children to have a positive attitudes towards writing, enjoy writing, enjoy what they are doing and not to fear to attempt things. This is also consistent with the ideas of Graves and others who aimed to develop in children a positive attitude towards writing, by letting them write what they want and what they know, particularly at early levels of schooling, avoiding over correction by teachers, which undermines self confidence, while being at hand to assist, to encourage, to praise the pupils, so that fear of criticism, rebuff or failure is absent (Turbill, 1982).

All teachers mentioned that publication, in addition to raising children's self confidence and pride in what they have done, could also demonstrate to the pupils that they wrote for real and meaningful purposes. The children write better when they have reason to do so. All teachers in this study reported that children love seeing their work published and seeing themselves as writers. This is in line with reports by Walshe (1981), and Turbill (1982), that publication boosts the children's egos, raises their confidence as learners and that children discover a great deal of self-motivation when they write for readers whom they believe will be interested or impressed by what they write.

Teachers A2, B, and C believed the conferences to be very important. In the conferences they could show the children that they valued their writing, that they wrote for a real purpose and that they could share ideas with the teacher as well as other children. Furthermore, they believed that the conference between peers could also help

children realise or learn that they had learnt from each other. These features are consistent with the function of the conference stated by Graves (1983), Walshe (1981), Turbill (1982) and Murray (1985). They see the conference as the central point of classroom interaction, where the children have opportunities to talk about their ideas, comment on their perceptions, and the teacher helps children to value what they know and what they have achieved.

It was stated by the teachers, particularly by Teacher C (grade 5/6), that during the conference children have a chance to explain what they mean, to clarify ideas, and to look into meanings further, and to gain confidence. This is consistent with Gordon (1986) who reports that by conferencing with other students and with teachers, students improve their reading, and clarify their ideas and expression, and Emmitt & Pollock (1991) who write that in individual or group conferences teachers can help children to become aware of their own intentions as writers.

Important information was also stated by Teacher B (grade 3/4), that conferences could be used to encourage children to revise their writing, particularly those students who did not want to revise, because in conferences children could hear and see the mistakes they had made. This statement demonstrates that it is not the case that teachers in the process approach do not want to intervene positively in children's writing because of the concept of ownership (Martin, 1985, in Richardson, 1991), and that teachers in the process conference approach do not teach language and the mechanics of writing as indicated by Walker (1987), Christie, Martin & Rothery (1989). Perhaps this is because these teachers have developed an eclectic approach.

The benefit of demonstration mentioned by Teacher A1 (grade 1), as a way to help children talk through thought processes and show the children how to write, is consistent with the writings of Murray (1982), Graves (1983), Turbill & Cambourne (1987), Education Department of Western Australia (1994a). They write that teachers should demonstrate writing to show the children that in writing, there is a process of

brainstorming, deciding a topic, writing, revising, editing, etc. With demonstrations, teachers can also show that normally no writer can get their writing right at the first draft and that redrafting helps make the writing better.

Teacher A1, like Calkins (1986), Graves (1983, 1985a), Turbill (1982), Egan (1984) and Clark (1987), considered daily writing time to be of great importance to give children a lot of opportunities to write and help the children grow to become writers, as “the more they write the better writers they become” (Teacher A1). Daily writing times allow children to sustain their interest (Calkins, 1986), to grow in all aspects of language studies (Clark, 1987), and help the children like writing because through daily writing the children can gain experience in choosing their topics, and realise that they have written a lot (Graves, 1983, 1985a). In addition, by offering children daily opportunities, the teacher can also talk to every child which gives her/him opportunities to gauge each child’s level, follow progress, and deal with difficulties at the moment of need.

Teachers B and C mentioned the importance of brainstorming, when every child’s ideas are accepted, and nothing is deemed wrong, or unacceptable. This brainstorming is important because not only does this show that each child’s ideas are accepted, which of course will strengthen the children’s self confidence, but it also shows the children, that in the writing process, there is a stage of brainstorming, when the writer thinks about the topic that they might want to write best.

Teacher A2 found ownership to be important because ownership allowed the children to write what they knew and hence felt confident about. This is in line with the writings of Graves (1983) and Rosen (1989) that children will write better and more self confidently when they write about what they know or their own experiences.

Another strength of the approach mentioned by the teacher was with respect to the concept of catering for individual differences. All teachers believed that with the

process-conference approach they could cater for every child, so children were able to develop individually, at their own rate, and at their own level. All children could produce something of their own. In addition, from a teaching point of view, as stated by Teacher A1, teaching writing individually is more organised and more interesting rather than teaching a whole group at once. In an individualised program children could go off and write what they were interested in.

The teachers' beliefs concerning the criticisms of the process approach

The second research question concerned the teachers' beliefs concerning the criticisms made of the process-conference approach.

Results from interviews with respect to the criticisms made of the process approach indicated that most of the criticisms were not believed to be valid criticisms by the teachers.

The first criticism investigated was that the process writing comes to be mainly story writing because teachers in the process-conference approach do not teach writing explicitly and do not induct the children into a variety of written language (Walker, 1987; Collerson 1989a; Christie, Martin & Rothery, 1989; Cope & Kalantzis, 1993).

Based on the teachers' interviews, this criticism was found to be the case only in grade 1. However, the teachers in grade 1 did not think they should be worried about it, because at this level, they said, the most important thing was to let the children write what they were secure in, and what they were comfortable with. In addition, the two teachers knew how meet the criticism by introducing some other types or genres of writing, like instructions, letters, or reports which the children wrote in the content areas such as science. The thing that they thought should be emphasised was the positive attitude towards writing and confidence "to have a go".

The fact that the teachers did not think that they should be worried about this criticism is consistent with the writings of Graves (1989a) that the wish to tell stories, to explain the world of wonder and terror around us is an essential part of being human. Children enjoy writing fiction and because children's first fiction so closely resembles play, children are unaware of the demands of the genre.

Teacher B and C did not think that the children in her class only wrote stories or personal recounts, because they also had some directive periods, in which the teacher assigned the topic and the genre. The children did a lot of writings, for example, writing a report or review of articles, or writing a letter. This is in line with the writings of Graves (1984a, 1989b, 1994) and Collerson (1989b) that although the process approach upholds the concept of free choice of topics, it does not mean that there is no place for the assigned topics and genre. It is important that the teacher assign the topic and the genre, and children be encouraged to have the experience of writing things which they have not chosen by themselves and to cope with the topics that come to them.

In relation to the criticism that teachers in the process approach do not teach about language, do not teach writing explicitly, do not intervene with the children's writing, important information was stated by Teacher B that "the process writing approach by itself is not the all end all; the teacher should also have the spelling and grammar correct. The teacher should still monitor what the children are writing, how they are writing, what grammatical, punctuation and spelling mistakes they've made." This statement has proved that the criticism was not justified for this teacher. The views expressed by Teacher B have shown that although content is emphasised in the process approach, it does not mean that the mechanics of writing, grammar and spelling are not considered to be important. This is in line with Barton (1994) who states that learning to write involves two aspects: "learning the mechanics of writing or becoming a scribe, and deciding what to write, or becoming an author" (p. 156).

The second criticism investigated was related to the concept of free choice of topics, and the notion that "free choice of topics creates children who write gender stereotypes and dominant social stereotypes and biases" (Kamler 1992, 1993). This criticism was the only one which was felt to be a reasonable comment by all teachers. However, Teacher A1 did not think that she had to be unduly worried about gender issues. She felt that it was more important at this early stage for the children to write freely. Teacher A2 said that this would happen only at the beginning, and she thought that girls and boys would write different things because boys and girls were different and they were interested in different things.

To avoid this gender stereotypical writing, teacher B often tried to channel them to another version, for example, by insisting on no blood, no killing, and no shooting. Teacher C, who found gender stereotypical writing only in a few cases, had explicit strategies to assist in counteracting such writing. For example, she encouraged children to write something which had strong characters for both boys and girls.

The third criticism that the children are not able to revise (Bartlett, 1982) was not believed to be evident by the teachers. Teacher A1 thought that it was still a difficult thing for the children in grade 1, but she tried to show them how to revise when the children had conferences with her. In addition, the teacher encouraged the children to give comments to each other, to learn to improve their writing. Teacher A2 and B did not believe in the criticism either, saying that some children know how to revise better than the others. Teacher A2 said that children at grade 1 level, who were already fairly proficient were ready to revise their own writing. To show the children how to revise, this teacher demonstrated revision and had children as a class help her write and revise. Teacher B tried to encourage the class to revise by encouraging them to look up a dictionary, to conference with peers, or to proofread their work in front of her, to make them aware of whether what they had written made sense, or whether they liked what they had written. Teacher C thought that as long as she demonstrated and taught

the children to revise, and the children were given strategies, they would start to develop their revisability and to edit on their own.

All the data above have shown that some children, even in grade 1 level are able to revise. This is in accord with Graves (1983) who states that children are already able to revise long before they go to school. This can be seen when they are playing; they rearrange the toy house, toy blocks.

The fourth criticism that "ownership and free choice of topics advantages only a certain group of children" was not believed to be evident in this study. In fact, all teachers believed the opposite to the criticism. The teachers found that the process approach allowed the children to develop at their own level. To help those students who struggled the teachers did give extra help. Teacher A1 gave the struggling children a story plan, on which they had to draw a picture of when they did something, with whom, and what they did, to help them organise their thoughts, their ideas, as strategy suggested by Graves (1989a). The teacher found that the poorest students benefited from this strategy.

Teacher A2 thought that those who developed slowly needed extra help, and she helped them by organising an intensive program, focusing on organisation, or the building of vocabularies.

Teacher B and C did not believe in the criticism at all. Teacher B found that even the children with very limited vocabulary were not afraid to put their thoughts down on paper. Although they made mistakes in spelling, they made sense of it, and they were not afraid to make mistakes. Teacher C claimed that when children were not at the grade level, it was not the problem of the approach.

All the teachers' statements were consistent with Gordon's writing (1986) that learning in the process-conference approach is inclusive of all students, because the approach

values the experience and language of each person, and respects a student's choice of topic and ownership of the work. She reports that students with varying abilities and interests consciously extend each other, and even students with minimal literacy can produce meaningful and attractive publications.

In response to the fifth criticism investigated in this study, "that individualised writing program ignores the fact that writing is a social activity" (Gilbert, 1989, 1990), all teachers revealed that they did not believe it to be a fair comment. They said that the children not only wrote individually, but also in groups, where they had to share ideas and help each other. In addition, there was always a place for social interaction, during and after the writing process. Children were encouraged to conference with the teacher or peers, publish and share their writing.

Again, what the teachers reported was in line with Graves (1985) who argues that writing is a public act; Murray (1982) who states that writing is a shared product; and Moffett (1983) who states that learning to use language requires feedback of human response. Even when one purports to be writing for oneself-for pure self-expression, one can not escape the ultimately social implications inherent in any use of language.

The application of the basic tenets of the process-conference approach

The third area of research concerned the application by the teachers of the principles of the process-conference approach.

A major feature of the observations was that the observed practices strongly matched the teachers' stated principles. This has shown that because the teachers' beliefs were very strong, they tried to do their best in applying the basic principles of the approach, and tried to follow the suggestions of the advocates of this approach.

All the basic tenets of the process-conference approach were applied in all classrooms observed. The basic principle that writing is treated as a process could be clearly seen in all classrooms, with all teachers demonstrating to the children how to write, not only writing stories (particularly for children in grade 1), but also writing letters and instructions, and writing in other content areas, like science, or social studies.

The process of writing taking place in each class could generally be divided into three stages: prewriting, writing, and postwriting (Britton, *et al*, 1975; Walshe, 1981; Murray, 1982). Prewriting is when the children and the teacher selected the topic, brainstormed, and demonstrated how to write, how to use punctuation. The writing stage is when the children individually or in groups write with the supervision of the teacher and the teacher held conferences with each child or group. The post-writing stage is when the children publish their piece and receive feedback from the audience of her/his piece. The writing process culminated in publication, when the children got their writing read, either by a real audience or by the teacher or friends.

The children, particularly in grade 1 and 3, did draw after writing, to describe what they had written. This is particularly important for the children in lower grades as rehearsal, as stated by Turbill (1982, 1983); Graves (1983, 1989); Stires, (1989) that drawing helps writing and helps children organise their ideas. For the children in lower grades, drawing is actually writing and functions as a means of clarifying and representing ideas.

The way teachers A1, A2 and B helped children to spell a word by sounding the word out, or by encouraging the children to invent the spelling, is really worthwhile, as invented spelling functions as a natural path a beginner can take in expressing thought confidently in writing before he or she knows how to spell (Turbill, 1982). Invented spelling also gives young writers power, as this will enable them not to worry about correct spelling on the first draft, and in fact, work like professional writers (Sowers, 1984).

The fact that all the teachers encouraged children to write based on what they knew, either in the topic chosen by themselves or assigned by the teacher is another aspect that demonstrated the teachers' understanding and belief about the process conference approach. This is in line with the approaches suggested by Sealey *et al* (1979), Graves (1983), Murray (1982, 1985), Rosen (1989), and many other writers that children will be able to write more confidently and comfortably when they write what they know, which can promote "rigorous learning", as "the most important thing children can learn is what they know and how they know it" (Graves, 1983, p. 72).

The characteristics of the process-writing classroom suggested by Cambourne & Turbill (1987) clearly existed in the observed classrooms, such as:

- the teacher encouraged the children to use the print surrounding the classroom;
- the teacher demonstrated how they wrote;
- the teacher encouraged the children to "have a go";
- the teacher let the children to take responsibility in what they wrote;
- the children were given time to write, and the children could get responses and constructive comments on their work, which could motivate them to better their writing.

The application of free choice of topics in all classrooms was similar. As stated by the teachers in the interviews, "free choice of topics" was not applied all the time the children wrote. Sometimes, particularly when the children were required to write in the content areas, the topic was assigned by the teacher based on the topic and the learning area. However, the concept that the children should write what they knew and what they had learnt was always applied. This could be seen, for example, when two children in grade 3/4 did not go to Tooradin were not expected to write about animals that had been seen and learnt in Tooradin Marine Centre. Instead, they were required to write about animals they knew.

All classes allowed for daily writing time where children wrote not only individually, but also in groups. The topic may have been about current issues, or newspaper articles, or, like in grade one, about the news or stories that children brought to the classroom. This is consistent with the practice advocated by Graves (1983, 1985a), and Calkins (1986) who advise that writing must be done every day, as regular writing helps children, among others, choose topics, listen to their pieces and revise. When children do not write every day, it is hard for them to sustain interest in their piece.

There was a slight difference in the application of the conference from grade to grade. In grade 1, most children conferenced only with the teacher. This could be seen from the fact that when they did not know how to spell a word, they tended to ask only to the teacher. Only some children asked other fellow students who were proficient spellers. This is different from observations in grade 3/4 and 5/6, in which the teacher encouraged the children to conference with peers. When the children did conference with the teacher, the teacher always asked them the question "whom did you do conference with? or who proofread your writing? This, as reported by Turbill (1982); Sangirardi-Gray & Meltzer (1994), was really fruitful. The higher the children's grade, the more reliant they become on their peers. In addition, the conference between peers can also help the teacher to organise time with individuals, particularly with those who need extra help. Moreover, peer conference is important because children could learn from each other and it can build self confidence and self reliance in student writers.

Publication, like the sending of the letter to the children's grandparents in grade 1, to NASA in grade 5/6, and other types of publication, like reading in front of the classroom was really beneficial. Publication really made the children enthusiastic about writing, and enhanced the students' self confidence as writers because they knew that their work had an audience who was interested in it.

At the publication stage, the teachers practised several things, namely:

- suggesting to the children that they write neatly, which was in line with the suggestion by Turbill (1982) that publication involves attractive presentation through neat handwriting, correct spelling, helpful punctuation, and good page-lay out;
- putting a date on children's work, or suggesting that the children write a date on their work; which enabled them to record the children's progress (Turbill, 1982); and
- letting the children read their piece in front of the classroom, or to the teachers themselves and friends, which constituted a valuable way of publication as suggested by Turbill (1982).

Not all children's work was published as a book or displayed in the classroom, or sent to a real audience (like a letter). This is consistent with comments by Graves (1983) who suggests that only about one piece in each of four to five pieces deserves publishing.

All teachers encouraged the children not to worry too much about the spelling and mechanics of writing at the first draft, and encouraged the children to write several drafts, to revise, and proofread, as suggested by Turbill (1982); Graves(1983); Walshe (1984), Harste *et al* (1984) and Calkins (1986). This has made the children confident to express their ideas, similar to professional writers, and has made the children realise that there is a process of writing which culminates in publication.

From the samples collected, and the process-conference approach to writing experienced by the children, it was clear that the children's writing ability improved from grade to grade. The children in grade one seemed to find it difficult to revise, so they still made a lot of mistakes in terms of spelling, and punctuation. However, the mastery of spelling and mechanics of writing of the children in grade 3/4, and especially in grade 5/6, was very much higher. Most students in grade 5/6 made only one or two mistakes, and some did not make mistakes at all in their writing. In addition, in grade 3/4, and particularly grade 5/6, the process of revising, and the concept that writing is a craft was clearly evident from the way the students revised. In

revising, the children in grade 3/4 and 5/6 were already able to indicate, where they realised that they should add some information or that they made mistakes - in punctuation, capitalisation and grammar. Furthermore, the children in grade 5/6 did not care too much about the neatness or aesthetic aspect of writing in the first draft, like professional writers do. This, based on my observations, was thanks to the fact that the teacher always encouraged the children to cross out when they revised, and she did not want them to "white out", so the process of revising could be clearly seen by her. This has made the children realise that there is a process in writing before they produced a neat final copy.

What the teacher did in encouraging children to cross out when revising their work, is consistent with Graves (1983) who suggests that the teacher should show the children how to control new information. He states that it is a significant moment when any child decides to cross out instead of erasing an error. This immediately signals that the paper is only a draft, that the text can be reworked.

In conjunction with the criticisms made of the process approach investigated in this study, the findings from the classrooms indicate several points as follows.

The fact that the children in all grades wrote in a variety of genres and wrote in other content areas (children in grade 1 wrote about science, and other types of genre - letter and instructions; children in grade 3/4 wrote about Anzac Day, gun laws and science, children in grade 5/6 wrote a letter related to the topic in science) has rejected the criticism that the process approach comes to be mainly story writing. In addition, the claim that the teacher in the process approach do not teach about language, do not teach about the mechanics of writing was not evident. All teachers in this study did demonstrate to the children and explained to the children about how to use punctuation, capitalisation, the characteristic of a genre (like Teacher A1 who explained the characteristics of an instruction, and the conventions of a letter), which was done either in front of the classroom to the whole class, or during the conference

individually. All teachers were also aware of the importance of the range of genre. This could be seen from the fact that they encouraged children to write not only stories, but also reports, letters, and procedures. These, as Collerson (1989b) states, empower children to gain access to power and success in the higher levels of education as it is the writing in such genres, especially report and essay writing that children will have to undertake in secondary and tertiary education.

Moreover, the claim that various steps of writing are not applied when writing in other content areas (Walker, 1987), was clearly not the case. From the observations, it is clear that every time the children wrote they passed through similar steps, starting from discussing, brainstorming, and culminating in publication, which was done in several ways, including reading in front of the classroom, reading the piece to the teacher or peers, displaying, or sending to the real audience.

With respect to the criticism that free choice of topic creates gender stereotypes and dominant social stereotypes, there was a slight difference between the results from the interviews and classroom observations. From the interviews, teachers believed that the criticism was reasonable. From the classroom observations, it was found that only in grade 1 did free choice of topics create gender stereotypical writing. That was when children wrote an instruction, with the topic chosen by themselves. The girls tended to write about how to plant or how make a sandwich, while boys tended to write about how to make a kite, how to make a sand house and how to make a block car. However, in other grades, this gender difference in writing was not evident. In addition, gender stereotypes were not evident when children wrote in the content areas or when they wrote in groups the members of which were both boys and girls.

The criticism that free choice of topics creates children who write gender stereotypes and social stereotypes and biases warrants further research to make it clear when, in what circumstances children write gender stereotypes, and what can be done to help children to become more aware of stereotypes.

The criticisms that children could not revise, and that even if they know they have a problem, they do not know how to solve it, were not supported either. The children in grade one seemed to have difficulty in revising; however, it was not the case for all children. The fact that children in grade 1 could give comments on their friends' writing, and they asked the teacher about the spelling of a certain words, they crossed out the word if the spelling was incorrect, indicated that they knew how to make their writing better. The children could carry out the two components of the revision processes mentioned by Bartlett (1982), which are: evaluation and correction.

Finally, the criticisms that the individualised writing program advantages only a certain group of children, and that the individualised writing program ignores the fact that writing is a social activity could not be justified in this research. The children did not only write individually, but also in groups when they had to work together and help each other; those who were advanced helped those who struggled; they read each other's writing; and they conferenced with peers or with the teacher. In addition, all children were enthusiastic about writing, about publishing their pieces; they were self confident when reading their piece in front of the classroom. These observations supported the report by Gordon (1986) who says that in the process approach learning is inclusive of all children.

Chapter 6

Conclusions and Implications for Future Research

Conclusions

This study investigated four teachers' beliefs and understandings about the process-conference approach, their beliefs concerning criticisms made of the approach, and the way they implemented the approach in their writing classrooms. From the results and discussions in the previous chapters, several conclusions can be drawn.

1. The beliefs and understandings of the teachers involved in this study were very strong. This conclusion is based on the observed classroom practices, the expected outcomes of their writing program, the positive attitudes towards writing that they wanted the children to develop, and their articulated principles about the process-conference approach. All the beliefs and practices were in accord with the major advocates of the approach. Indeed no major differences were noted in the teachers' beliefs and in the way they applied the basic tenets of the process approach to writing. Principles and practices matched!
2. All the major features of the process-conference approach were believed to be fruitful by all the teachers in helping children to develop as writers. These particularly included:
 - demonstration: this was where the teacher showed the children how to write, how to revise, how to brainstorm, how to select their topics;
 - free choice of topics: this was to enable children to write what they know, as the children will feel comfortable when they write about their own experiences;
 - the conference: this was an opportunity for the teacher and a child or a group of children to discuss pieces of writing, and an opportunity for the children to receive feedback. The conference did not always include the teacher, as it might be a conference with peers;

- daily writing time: this was to give the children the opportunity to write as frequently as possible, in the belief that the more the children write, the better writers they will become.
- publication: this was to encourage children's pride in their writing and to show the children that they wrote for a meaningful purpose.

3. The characteristics of the writing classroom stated by the advocates of the approach were observed in each of the classrooms, where all the teachers encouraged children to become involved; to "have a go" at writing. Children were surrounded with print; children were given time to practise writing; children were given freedom to choose what they wanted to write; teachers demonstrated to the children how they selected the topic, how they wrote and how they revised their writing; teachers did not expect the children's work to be right at the first draft; teachers always valued the writing the children had produced.
4. Of all the criticisms of the approach examined, only one criticism was believed by all teachers in this study to be valid and that was that the free choice of topic creates children who write in gender stereotypical fashion. However, all the teachers felt they knew how to compensate for the problem, by having children work in groups, and thus ensuring the sharing of ideas from girls and boys, and from children from various backgrounds.

In relation to the criticism that free choice of topics produces gendered stereotypical writings, there was a very interesting finding. On the one hand, all the teachers believed that this criticism was valid. However, from the classroom observations, only one incident of such writing was recorded. That was in grade 1A, when children wrote an instruction with the topic chosen by themselves. The boys wrote about making books, cars, kites, and the girls wrote about cooking, sewing, and planting.

Another criticism that was felt to be valid, but only by teachers in grade 1 was that the process-conference approach concentrates on recount or story writing. However, the teachers believed that this happened only in the early years of schooling, as even in grade 1 the teachers had introduced some other types of genre, such as a letter, an instruction, a list. In addition, the teachers did not think they should be unduly concerned about the criticism, because the major aim in the early grades was to encourage the children to develop a positive attitude to writing and write about what they know in order that the children will perceive themselves as writers. Teachers in grade 3/4 and 5/6 did not feel this was a justifiable criticism, as in addition to stories, children were also required to write a variety of genres, such as reports or exposition, particularly in key learning areas such as science and social studies.

The other criticisms studied were not believed to be valid by the teachers in this study. In relation to the criticism concerning the revision of children's writing, one teacher believed, even in grade one, although it is still a difficult thing, that with the teacher encouragement, the children could give comments on other children's writing, to assist in making it better. This was evident from the classroom observations, that children in grade 1 could give comments on other children's writing. The other teacher in grade 1 believed that many confident writers, were also ready to revise their pieces. Teachers in grade 3/4 and 5/6 believed that the ability to revise should be explicitly taught, so they should encourage the children to revise, for example, by asking questions to them as at conferences with the teacher. This was particularly important for those who did not want to revise. When they could hear that their ideas did not make sense, or that they had made mistakes in punctuation, spelling or grammar, they saw the need for revision.

The criticism that the concept of authorship advantages only a certain group of children, was not believed to be valid by any of the teachers. The teachers said that the process approach enables those who were advanced to go further, and those who struggled to "have a go". In so doing it, the approach caters for every child.

Furthermore, the teachers did not believe in the criticism that individualised writing program ignores the fact that writing is a social activity. They said that there were many ways which could be used to show that writing is a social process, for children wrote not only individually, but also in groups, and they helped each other, read each other's work, conferenced, either with the teacher or other peers, and published their writing for other children to read and share. Writing in these classrooms is very much a social activity. The environment of a community of writers was fostered.

5. From the samples of children's work, it was clear that children's writing ability was improving from grade to grade. This was particularly evident by the children's ability in revising their writing. Where children in grade one did little revision, children in grade 3/4, and particularly in grade 5/6, were aware of the process of revision, and they were able to insert data, to find their mistakes and to correct the mistakes by themselves.
6. The strong beliefs and understandings of the concept of the process-conference approach teachers hold is very important, as it is only when they have very clear principles and understandings, that they can fully apply the concepts. This was the case with the teachers in this study, who could apply the process approach confidently in different grade levels because they did have a very strong and detailed knowledge about the process-conference approach.

Implications for future research

Three areas of worthwhile research were noted.

1. This study did not include formal interviews with students. The main goals of the process approach is to produce confident and competent writers and students who

enjoy writing. Further research with the focus on students' achievement and particularly their attitudes to writing is warranted and would be very fruitful.

2. All the teachers in this study felt that the criticism that free choice of topics produces gender stereotypical writing. However, in the classrooms observed, the process conference approach allowed the children to work together, to get to know each other, boys and girls, which in fact could diminish gender stereotypes. This could be seen from the fact gender stereotypical writings were noticed only once in this study, that was in grade 1. Additional research into the frequency when children write gender stereotypical texts, and the way the teachers cope with such texts would be a valuable area of research.
3. It was noticed that some children who worried too much about the exact spelling tended to write slowly. Research on the relationship between the spelling competency and the speed, the fluency and the quantity of writing is warranted and would be valuable.

Concluding remarks

Success in schooling depends to a large extent on writing. This research on the implementation of the process-conference approach to writing in Victorian schools is very encouraging, for the children are clearly developing into confident and competent writers. It would be best that such an approach is introduced to Indonesian schools to help raise the standard in primary schooling. With the emphasis on authorship as well as the mechanics of writing, the process-conference approach allows children to develop not only as scribes, but also as authors. In addition, with the teacher's encouragement to write in a variety of genres (in addition to writing stories), the process-conference approach enables children to develop all the potential uses of writing, which is not only for the satisfaction of personal needs and wishes, such as writing personal recounts, but also social, such as to keep in touch with other people

(writing letters), to gain and handle information (writing reports), to help other people to do something (writing instructions). Furthermore, as it is writing in a variety of genre that children will be required to do in the higher levels of education, and in their life in the society, the process-conference approach can empower children to gain access and success in their future education and their life.

The approach does not require great financial outlays but does require commitment and understandings of the principles of the approach and hence as teacher education will be the primary challenge for the Indonesian education system. This is however a challenge that must be met, for Indonesia needs to raise the literacy levels of the population to face the technology age of the next millennium. The traditional method, while good, are not sufficient to achieve the literacy levels that are required. The process-conference approach to writing offers one very sound and proven method that could be implemented immediately in Indonesia.

Chapter 7

Summary

This study investigated the beliefs and strategies of four Victorian teachers conducting exemplary writing programs by using the process-conference approach to writing. The results of the study demonstrate that the process-conference approach has become an impressive approach for developing confident and competent writers. Unlike the traditional method, which emphasised the form of writing first rather than the content, the process-conference approach emphasises the content (the authoring aspect of writing) first rather than the form (the scribing aspect of writing). This allows more opportunity for children to develop not only as scribes but also as authors.

There have been changes and evolution in the process-conference approach, which have particularly been influenced by another approach which is popular in Australia, that is the genre-based approach to writing. The changes, as indicated by Graves (1984a, 1989b, 1994), were included in the process-conference approach used by the teachers in this study, particularly in terms of the emphasis on writing a broader range of nonfiction genre. Therefore, criticisms that might have been valid in the mid-eighties, were not justified in this study. Teachers have developed the process-conference approach, and have adopted some of the principles of the genre theories to avoid the concentration on recounts and narratives that predominated in the early process-conference writing classrooms.

This study also found that the basic tenets of the process-conference approach were strongly believed to be fruitful by the teachers and were clearly established in the classrooms observed. However, the process-conference approach is still an evolving theory and not a static set of beliefs. There is always a possibility of changes and evolution of the approach and this makes it a most suitable method for teaching writing, and one that is clearly successful in leading children to develop their writing ability and helping them succeed in their learning.

Bibliography

Ary, D., Jacobs, L.C., & Razavieh, A. (1972). *Introduction to research education*. New York: Holt, Rinehart & Winston.

Bartlett, E. J. (1982). "Learning to revise: Some component processes." In M. Nystrand. (Ed). *What writers know. The language, process, and structure of written discourse*. New York: Academic Press.

Barton, D. (1994). *Literacy: An introduction to the ecology of written language*. Blackwell: Oxford.

Bean, W., & Bouffler, C. (1987). *Spell by writing*. Rozelle, NSW: PETA.

Board of Studies. (1995). *Curriculum and Standards Framework. English*. Melbourne: The Board Of Studies.

Borg, W. R., & Gall, M. D. (1990). *Educational research. An introduction. Second edition*. New York: David Mc. Kay Company, Inc.

Bright, R. (1995). *Writing instruction in the intermediate grades: What is said, what is done, what is understood*. Newark, Delaware: IRA.

Britton, J., Burgess, T., Martin, N., McLeod, A., Rosen, H. (1975). *The development of writing abilities (11-18)*. London: Macmillan Education Ltd.

Calaghan, M., Knapp, P., & Noble, G. (1993). "Genre in practice." In B. Cope, & M. Kalantzis. (Eds). *The powers of literacy: A genre approach to teaching writing*. London: The Falmer Press.

Calkins, L. M. (1984). "When children learn to punctuate: Basic skills belong in context." In R. D. Walshe. (Ed). *Donald Graves in Australia. "Children want to write."* Rozelle, NSW: PETA.

Calkins, L. M. (1986). *The art of teaching writing*. Portsmouth, NH: Heinemann.

Calkins, L. M. (1991). *Living between the lines*. Portsmouth, NH: Heinemann.

- ✓ Cambourne, B., & Turbill, J. (1987). *Coping with chaos*. Rozelle, NSW: PETA.
- ✓ Christie, F., Martin, J. R., & Rothery, J. (1989). "Genres make meaning." In *English in Australia*. (90). 43-57.
- Clark, R. P. (1987). *Free to write. A journalist teaches young writers*. Portsmouth, NH: Heinemann.
- Coe, R. M. (1986). "Teaching writing: The process approach, humanism, and the context of 'crisis'." In S. D. Castell., A. Luke, & K. Egan. (Eds). *Literacy, society and schooling. A reader*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Cohen, L., & Manion, L. (1980). *Research methods in education*. London: Croom Helm.
- Cohen, L., & Manion, L. (1985). *Research methods in education*. (Second edn). London: Croom Helm.
- ✓ Collerson, J. (1989a). "Building on the process." In J. Collerson. (Ed). *Writing for life*. Rozelle, NSW: PETA.
- Collerson, J. (1989b). "Writing for life." In J. Collerson. (Ed). *Writing for life*. Rozelle, NSW: PETA.
- ✓ Coleman, A., Kalantzis, M., Kress, G., Martin, J., Poynting, S., Slade, D., Wignell, P. (1987). *Social literacy. Monograph 33. The fundamentals of literacy: Where will the writing K-12 document take us?* Sydney: Common Ground Publishing.
- Connole, H. (1993). "The research enterprise." In H. Connole., B. Smith., & R. Wiseman. *Research methodology 1: Issues and methods in research. Study guide*. Melbourne: Deakin University.
- ✓ Cope, B., & Kalantzis, M. (1993). "The power of literacy and the literacy of power." In B. Cope, & M. Kalantzis. (Eds). *The powers of literacy: A genre approach to teaching writing*. London: The Falmer Press.
- Edelsky, C. (1994). "Education for democracy." In Deakin University. (1996). *Language, literacy and learning A. Reader*. Melbourne: Deakin University.
- ✓ Education Department of Western Australia. (1994a). *Writing. Resource book*. Melbourne: Longman Australia, Pty. Ltd.

- Education Department of Western Australia. (1994b). *Writing. Developmental continuum*. Melbourne: Longman Australia Pty. Ltd.
- Egan, J. E. (1984). "Making time for writing." In R. D. Walshe. (Ed). *Donald Graves in Australia. "Children want to write..."* Rozelle, NSW: PETA.
- Emmitt, M. & Pollock, J. (1991). *Language and learning*. Melbourne: Oxford University Press.
- Field, P., & Morse, J. (1985). "Interview Techniques." In R. Wiseman.(1993). *Research methodology 1: Issues and methods in research. Reader part 2*. Melbourne: Deakin University.
- Gilbert, P., & Rowe, K. (1989). *Gender, literacy and the classroom*. Melbourne: Australian Reading Association.
- Gilbert, P. (1990). "Authorising disadvantage: authorship and creativity in the language classroom." In F. Christie. (Ed). *Literacy for a changing world*. Melbourne: ACER.
- Gilbert, P. (1993). *Gender stories and the language classroom*. Melbourne: Deakin University.
- Gordon, S. (1986). "The introduction of the conference writing process at Exhibition High School." In *English in Australia*. (75). 23-26.
- Graves, D. H. (1983). *Writing: Teachers and children at work*. London: Heinemann.
- Graves, D. H.(1984a). *A researcher learns to write. Selected articles and monographs*. Exeter, NH: Heinemann.
- Graves, D. H.(1984b). "What children show us about revision." In R. D. Walshe. (1984). (Ed). *Donald Graves in Australia. "Children want to write."* Rozelle, NEW: PETA.
- Graves, D. H. (1984c). "Patterns of child control of the writing process." In R. D. Walshe. (Ed).*Donald Graves in Australia. "Children want to write."* Rozelle, NSW: PETA.
- Graves, D. H.(1985a). "All children can write." In B. M. Power, & R. Hubbard (1991). *Literacy in process*. Portsmouth, NH: Heinemann.

- Graves, D. H. (1985b). "The enemy is orthodoxy." In M. Maguire., & A Pare. (Eds). *Patterns of development*. Canada: The Canadian Council of Teachers of English.
- Graves, D. H. (1986). "Writing process has growing pains." In D. Graves., R.D, Walshe., B. Dwyer., D. Snowball., L. Lodge., J. Barrow., M. Fox., M. Trim., A. Jager. *Children writing. Process-conference writing*. Melbourne: Primary Education.
- Graves, D. H.(1989a). *The reading/writing teacher's companion. Experiment with fiction*. Toronto: Irwin Publishing.
- Graves, D. H. (1989b). *The reading writing teacher's companion. Investigate nonfiction*. Portsmouth, NH: Heinemann.
- Graves, D. H. (1994). *A fresh look at writing*. Portsmouth, NH: Heinemann.
- Hakim, C. (1987). "Case studies." In H. Connole. (Ed). (1993). *Research methodology 1: Issues and methods in research. Reader: Part 1*. Melbourne: Deakin University.
- Hall, N. (1989). "Introduction." In N. Hall. (Ed.).*The emergence of authorship in young children*. London: Hodder & Stoughton.
- Hall, N., & Robinson, A. (1994). "Power and control in young children's writing." In M. Hamilton., D. Barton., & R. Ivanic. *Worlds of literacy*. Clevedon: Multilingual Matters Ltd.
- Hapman, J. L. Jnr. (1968). *Research in education*. Ohio: Merrill Publishing Company.
- Harste, J. C., Woodward, V. A., & Burke, C. L. (1984). *Language stories and literacy lessons*. Portsmouth, NH: Heinemann.
- Hopkins, C. D.(1980).*Understanding educational research*. Ohio: Merrill Publishing Company.
- Jensen, J. M. (1993). "What do we know about the writing of elementary school children?" In Deakin University. (1995). *Literacies and education. Reader*. Melbourne: Deakin University
- Johnson, E. D. (1973). *Communication. An introduction to the history of writing, printing, books and libraries*. New Jersey: The Scarecrow Press, Inc.
- Kamler, B. (1992). "The social construction of free topic choice in the process writing classroom." *The Australian Journal of Language and Literacy*. 15(2), 105-119.

- Kamler, B. (1993). "Constructing gender in the process writing classroom." In Deakin University. (1995). *Literacies and education: Writing, Reader, Reading 2.1*. Melbourne: Deakin University.
- Kane, T. S. (1983). *The Oxford guide to writing. A rhetoric and handbook for college students*. New York: Oxford University Press.
- Kress, G. (1993). "Genre as social process." In B. Cope., & M. Kalantzis. (Eds). *The powers of literacy. A genre approach to teaching writing*. London: The Falmer Press.
- Martin, J. R. (1986). "Systemic functional linguistics and an understanding of written text." In J. Martin., & J. Rothery. *Working papers in linguistics. No. 4*. Sydney: Linguistics Department of University of Sydney.
- Mc Donald, L. (1991). "Parents in the classroom." In V. Nicoll., & L. Wilkie. (Eds). *Literacy at home and school. A guide for parents*. Rozelle, NSW: PETA.
- Moffett, J. (1981). *Active voice. A writing program across the curriculum*. New Jersey: Boynton/Cook Publishers, Inc.
- Moffett, J. (1983). *Teaching the universe of discourse*. Boston: Houghton Mifflin Company.
- ✓ Moss, P. (1981). *Writing matters*. Sydney: St Clair Press.
- ✓ Murray, D. M. (1982). *Learning by teaching (Selected articles on writing and teaching)*. Montclair/Boynton: Cook Publishing Inc.
- Murray, D. M. (1984). *Write to learn*. New York: Holt, Rinehart & Winston.
- ✓ Murray, D. M. (1985). *A writer teaches writing*. Second edition. New Jersey: Houghton Mifflin Company.
- Murray, D. M. (1989). *Expecting the unexpected. Teaching myself and others to read and write*. Portsmouth, NH: Boynton/Cook Publishers.
- Murray, D. M. (1990). *Shoptalk: learning to write with writers*. Portsmouth, NH: Boynton/Cook Publishers.
- New South Wales Department of Education, Literacy and Education Network and Directorate of Studies. (1990a). *A genre-based approach to teaching writing in years 3-6. An approach to writing K-12. Book 1. Introduction*. Annandale, NSW: Common Ground.

- New South Wales Department of Education, Literacy and Education Network and Directorate of Studies. (1990b). *A genre-based approach to teaching writing in years 3-6. An approach to writing K-12. Book 2. Factual writing.* Annandale, NSW: Common Ground.
- New South Wales Department of Education, Literacy and Education Network and Directorate of Studies. (1990c). *A genre-based approach to teaching writing in years 3-6. An approach to writing K-12. Book 3. Writing stories.* Annandale, NSW: Common Ground.
- New South Wales Department of Education, Literacy and Education Network and Directorate of Studies. (1990d). *A genre-based approach to teaching writing in years 3-6. An approach to writing K-12. Book 4. Theory and practice.* Annandale, NSW: Common Ground.
- Olson, B. V. L. (1990). "The revising of sixth grade writers with and without peer feedback." In *Journal of Educational Research*. 84. (1). 22-29.
- Parry, J. A., & Hornsby, D. (1985). *Write on: A conference approach to writing.* Portsmouth, NH: Heinemann.
- Richardson, P. (1991). "Language as personal resource and as social construct: Competing views of literacy pedagogy in Australia." In Deakin University. (1995). *Literacies and education: Writing. Reader.* Melbourne: Deakin University.
- Rivalland, J. (1991). "Writing development." In *Australian Journal of Reading*. 14.(4). 290-306.
- Rosen, H. (1971). "Towards a language policy across the curriculum." In D. Barnes, J. Britton., & H. Rosen. (1971). *Language, the learner and the school.* Melbourne: Penguin Education.
- Rosen, M. (1989). *Did I hear you write?* Ontario: Scholastic.
- Rothery, J. (1986a). "Teaching writing in the primary school: A genre based approach to the development of writing abilities." In J. R. Martin, & J. Rothery. *Working papers in linguistics. No. 4.* Sydney: Linguistics Department of University of Sydney.
- ✓ Rothery, J. (1986b). "Writing to learn and learning to write." In J. R. Martin, & J. Rothery. *Working papers in linguistics. No. 4.* Sydney: Linguistics Department of University of Sydney.

- Rothery, J. (1986c). "Let's teach children to write." In J. R. Martin, & J. Rothery. *Working papers in linguistics. No. 4*. Sydney: Linguistics Department of University of Sydney.
- Sangirardi-Gray, J. A., & Meltzer, E. (1993). "Organic mechanics: Developing skills through literature and student writing." In B. E. Cullinan. (Ed). *Pen in hand: Children become writers*. Newark, Delaware: IRA.
- Schroder, V. C. & Lovett, A. K. (1993). "Modelling the process approach in the early elementary grades." In B. E. Cullinan. (Ed). *Pen in hand*. Newark, Delaware: IRA.
- Sealey, L., Sealey, N., & Millmore, M. (1979). *Children's writing. An approach for the primary grades*. Newark, Delaware: IRA.
- Sowers, S. (1984). "Kids can write sooner than we think." In R. D. Walshe. (Ed). *Donald Graves in Australia. "Children want to write."* Rozelle, NSW: PETA.
- Stake, E. (1985). "Case study." In J. Nisbet., J. Megarry., & S. Nisbet. (Eds). *World yearbook of education 1985. Research, policy and politics*. London: Nicholas Publishing Company.
- Stires, S. (1989). "Thinking throughout the process. Self evaluation in writing." In J. M. Jensen. (Ed). *Stories to grow on. Demonstration of language learning in K-8 classroom*. Portsmouth, NH: Heinemann.
- Taft, R. (1989). "Ethnographic research method." In R. Wiseman. (Ed). *Research methodology 1: Issues and methods in research. Reader part 2*. Melbourne: Deakin University.
- Taylor, J. (1973). *Reading and writing in the first school*. London: George Allen And Unwin Ltd.
- The Education Department of Western Australia. (1995). *Writing. Resource book*. Melbourne: Longman Australia Pty. Limited.
- ✓ Thomson, J. (1978). "Language in the classroom." In D. Barnes, J. Thomson, & K. Watson. *Language in the classroom*. Melbourne: ALAA.

- Troyka, L. Q. (1987). *Handbook for writers*. New Jersey: Prentice-Hall, Inc.
- Turbill, J. (1982). *No better way to teach writing!* Rozelle, NSW: PETA.
- Turbill, J. (1983). *Now, we want to write!* Rozelle, NSW: PETA.
- Turbill, J., & Butler, A. (1984). *Towards a reading-writing classroom*. Rozelle, NSW: PETA.
- Turbill, J. (1991). "The teaching of writing: Process writing explained." In V. Nicoll, & L. Wilkie. (Eds). *Literacy at home and school. A guide for parents*. Rozelle, NSW: PETA.
- Turner, L. (1994). *Foundations for language teaching*. Melbourne: Deakin University.
- ✓ Walker, I. (1987). "Process writing in the content areas." In *Australian Journal of Reading*. 10 (4). 243-253.
- Walshe, R.D. (1977). "The process of writing." In R. D. Walshe. (Ed). *Better reading/writing-now!* Rozelle, NSW: PETA.
- Walshe, R. D. (1980). *101 questions primary teachers ask ... and 101 answers*. Rozelle, NSW: PETA.
- ✓ Walshe, R. D. (1981). *Every child can write*. Rozelle, NSW: PETA.
- ✓ Walshe, R. D., Shirley, D., O'Meara, P. (1984). *How to study better and pass exams confidently*. Melbourne: Longman Cheshire Pty. Ltd.
- Walshe, R. D. (1984). "Donald Graves in Australia." In R. D. Walshe. (1984). (Ed). *Donald Graves in Australia. "Children want to write."* Rozelle, NSW: PETA.
- ✓ Walshe, R. D. (1986a). "Writing to learn." In R. D. Walshe., P. March., & D. Jensen. (Eds). *Writing and learning in Australia*. Melbourne: Dellasta, Pty. Ltd.

- Walshe, R. D. (1986b). "Progression in writing to learn, K-12." In R. D. Walshe., P. March., & D. Jensen. (Eds). *Writing and learning in Australia*. Melbourne: Dellasta, Pty. Ltd.
- Walshe, R.D. (1986c). "The new approach to creative writing." In D. Graves., R.D, Walshe., B. Dwyer., D. Snowball., L. Lodge., J. Barrow., M. Fox., M. Trim., A. Jager. *Children writing. Process-conference writing*. Melbourne: Primary Education.
- Weightman, R.(1991). "What's all this 'genre' stuff?" In V. Nicoll, & L. Wilkie. (Eds). *Literacy at home and school. A guide for parents*. Rozelle, NSW: PETA.
- Well, G. (1986). *The meaning makers: Children learning language using language*. Portsmouth, NH: Heinemann.
- White, J. (1990). "On literacy and gender." In F. Christy. (Ed). *Literacy for a changing world*. Melbourne: ACER.
- Wilkinson, A. (1986). *The quality of writing*. Milton Keynes: Open University Press.

Appendix

Teachers' Responses to The Interview

Teachers' beliefs and understandings about the process-conference approach

Teacher A1

Question 1: How many years of teaching experience have you got? In what grade levels?

12 years, primarily teaching lower primary, prep to two.

Question 2: If you are asked to characterise your writing program, what would you say?

My writing program is changing. At this grade level (grade 1), I used to only emphasise writing diaries, recounting, say we go on an excursion, retelling. But now, I realise that younger children are just as capable of doing more difficult things, like writing a weather report, instructions, letters, and we're trying some different skills. Now I have always been in the belief that young children can do that if you demonstrate how you do it, you take them step by step.

Question 3: What are your chief goals in helping children to write?

I think my very chief goal is letting them have more confidence in themselves, to have a go, to try. I just want to give them the opportunity and help develop their confidence in writing.

Question 4: What kind of attitudes would you want your children to have?

Oh, positive, ... be willing to have a try, not be afraid to make mistakes because I try to explain to them that we learn through mistakes. Just to be positive about it, to enjoy it.

Question 5: In general, what do you think are the strengths of the process approach?

This process is more organised, in that we do not teach a whole group at once. The days of teaching a whole group at once are gone. I think this way is more interesting way of teaching writing because the children can go off and write what they were interested in, not just what the teacher wants them to write about.

Demonstration helps children talk through thought processes, learn how to organise their thoughts. ... If we show them, we help children who are good at listening, as well as watching.

Publication makes the children realise that they write for real purpose, and when they write for real purpose (for example writing a letter to their nanny), they write better, because they have the reason to do it, not because the teacher teaches them.

Daily writing time gives children a lot of opportunities to write. Writing is like reading. If they don't write often, or read often, they can't learn to read or write. The more they read, the better they become readers, and the more they write, the better they become writers. In the classroom, particularly in integrated study time, writing does happen just in writing session. In science, for example, they have to write a little report on what they have learnt.

Teacher A2

Question 1: How many years of teaching experience have you got? In what grade levels?

20 years, teaching in all grade levels, except for grade 3, and many years in grade 1.

Question 2: If you are asked to characterise your writing program, what would you say?

Whole language, emphasising it as a whole, not emphasising any of the particular areas of language, covering everyone of them, using and finding the children's strengths and helping them build on those.

Question 3: What are your chief goals in helping children to write?

To give them a lot of experience in every sort of writing, such as a story writing that we're used to doing, in all different areas of writing, and just help them express themselves.

Question 4: What kind of attitudes would you want your children to have?

I want them to enjoy what they are doing. If they're enjoying what they're doing, they're enjoying learning, they will learn a lot more than if they are unhappy.

Question 5: In general, what do you think are the strengths of the process approach?

I think in an individualised program, we cater for every child at their level and we can work in an easy way to manage catering for individual children. If the teacher teaches just in one group, it doesn't cater for all children because there are some children who have gone further.

Publication can show that we value their writing and that they write for purpose and that children share ideas. Children love seeing their work.

Ownership is a very important part of the approach, to make children realise that they are doing it by themselves. We have gone into a stage where we know we have some ownership on something. With the ownership, we're more prepared to try a bit hard or work at the better level, because children feel very confident and they write more easily when they write about what they know, that they have ownership to their own writing, rather than someone else telling them all the time. On the contrary, when the topic is new, and the children do not know a lot about it, the children find it difficult to write.

In the conference, we can also show the children that we value their writing and they write for purpose and they share ideas.

Teacher B

Question 1: How many years of teaching experience have you got? In what grade levels?

30 years, in all grade levels and every specialist, 12 years emergency teaching.

Question 2: If you are asked to characterise your writing program, what would you say?

Whole language approach, writing with purpose, to encourage children to have their opinions, to think about topics that are happening around them. We always start with the child-centered ideas-what they know about the topic, and we go from there. We also usually select the topic, but basically starting from the child.

Question 3: What are your chief goals in helping children to write?

Help them express themselves and their ideas, to gain confidence in themselves and know that they can write. Children with difficulty are helped to build up their confidence and skills. In addition, my goal is for them to be able to write confidently, to proofread their work, to recognise that they have some work which doesn't look right, to recognise that they should have some full stop in some place, and commas in others.

Question 4: What kind of attitudes would you want your children to have?

To enjoy their writing process, to enjoy putting their thought down the paper and to be really pleased with their final product.

Question 5: In general, what do you think are the strengths of the process approach?

The strength of the process approach is the flexibility of the children to write based on their ability. They don't have to produce stereotypes, like "you must write 10 lines." In addition, I find that I am not as rigid as I was. It's fine when children produce a short piece of writing, but they are happy with that, and they feel they've got their message across. So, the children can produce something of their own. Furthermore, the children have a purpose for what they're doing, make sense for them, and the children enjoy writing because writing has meant something to them. They write because they want to do it, or they want to find out something which is interest to them.

However, we have got to be very careful that the process writing approach by itself is not to be all and end all. You still have to have your spelling and your grammar. You still have got to monitor what children are writing, how they are writing and what grammatical and spelling mistakes they have made.

Brainstorming enables children to see how every one's idea is accepted, nothing wrong, nothing unacceptable, and by giving the children a chance to write several times, children will know that there is a stage to make their writing better.

In conference, we can show the value of what the children have really done their very best, and we can give them courage to try. By doing conference, we can also try to do justice for all, we learn from each other, we realise that we don't cover everything. Moreover, conferencing is important to help children who do not want to revise. When they read their piece, reading them aloud, they can actually hear where they have made mistakes, where they're leaving out words, etc.

Publication enables children to sort of have pride in their ability to produce their work. When they see a finished product, they really do. "Oh, I've done that. This is my work, I will get all that published."

Teacher C

Question 1: How many years of teaching experience have you got? In what grade levels?

2 years, in grade 5/6.

Question 2: If you are asked to characterise your writing program, what would you say?

My writing program is very child-centered and we give them a lot of different sorts of styles of writing, different genres, encourage them to do a lot of editing, on their own or with peers and then I am involved in the process, but only as a model, or to help them with the final editing.

Question 3: What are your chief goals in helping children to write?

My aim is to make them not have fear in writing, they're happy to attempt things. When they look at their work, they'll improve it, and their clarity and presentation, in the long run are developing as writers.

Question 4: What kind of attitudes would you want your children to have?

To be willing to take a risk, a try, happy to attempt things.

Question 5: In general, what do you think are the strengths of the process approach?

Children are able to develop individually, at their own pace, at their own level. In addition, with expectations placed on them, they tend to bring to writing more than their experiences, more than their own styles.

The conference has enormous benefits. They are not just saying a piece of work, then just correcting it. With the conference they have a chance to explain what they mean, to look into the meaning further, to clarify their ideas, their writing, and to have someone tutoring their work as well. I think it's really beneficial.

Brainstorming is also important, but we need to use a variety of ways of brainstorming still, not only writing on the board. Brainstorming also needs to develop into categorising into certain areas according to the agreed purpose of writing.

Children also love publishing their work. They love to see themselves as writers and publishers. When they've finished, sometimes they take it around to other grades.

Process writing is excellent, but we need time, to add time when the children need it, like teaching grammar when the children need it.

Teachers' beliefs concerning the criticisms made of the process approach

Teacher A1

Question 1: In the process approach, where the children are allowed to write with the topic from their own, do you find your children write only stories with the same topic over and over again?

I think in grade one they do, because that's what they're familiar with. But I don't think in grade prep, one and two you should worry about it. I think you start introducing the types. Surely, if it happens in grade 5 or 6, I would be worried, but my feeling is in year 1 you're just trying to introduce them a different type. But you still want them to do a lot of writing, so, let them write what they're comfortable with. In your guided sessions, like I did yesterday (referring to the session when she taught instruction), that's when you can have them try a different type, but in their free session, let them try to write in the area that they feel comfortable with. My feeling is I'm trying to get them to be positive about writing.

Question 2: Do you also find that free choice of topics creates children who write gender stereotypes?

In grade one they do, but I don't think we should be worried about it.

Question 3: During the process of writing, particularly in revising stage, are your children able to revise and improve their writing?

In year 1, it is a very difficult thing. What I have shown what my children to do is to underline the word they were very unsure of. And then, when we conference, I show them how to write properly. Sometimes, I let other children comment, and they do it in a positive way. Probably when the comments come from us, the children will get hurt, but if it comes from the children, they don't take it, and I think probably coming from the children is easier.

Question 4: Do you also think that the process approach advantages only a certain group of children? Do you find some children who do not succeed in their learning to write?

Children who are doing well at school do better at this program. With the children who are struggling with them, we have to give them extra help, and give them ideas on how we start stories, how we get our ideas in our head, how we organise our thoughts. One thing that I've given to my children is a story plan. They have to draw a picture of 'when they did something, who they did it with, when they went and what they did.' I find my poorest students benefit from this, because it helps organise what they're going to say, then they could use the pictures to write their stories. So, it is very useful.

I suppose, dealing individual children at what level they are, hopefully, in this way, there is no child will feel a failure. The children who are already to go ahead, you can make them comfortable go to the next step, the children that are struggling, you just help them as they are ready to be helped.

Question 5: Do you find that the individualised program, like the process approach ignores the fact that writing is a social process/ activity?

When we do integrated studies, we do group work, where the group has to write a report. So, writing happens all day, it is not just in writing session. For example, when we are doing science, I'll have the children write a report as a group.

Teacher A2

Question 1: In the process approach, where the children are allowed to write with the topic from their own, do you find your children write only stories with the same topic over and over again?

They do it at the beginning because they write what they're secure in, from the point of their experiences. But if you use activities and immerse them in enough activities, they will learn on and develop on from that. But, yes, at the start, they will tend to stick to the one topic they're confident in. So, you have to try to build their confidence to have a go at different areas and give them a variety of genres, and take a few risks. When you teach, for example, space, in science class, a lot of writings have been done, like a report writing, writing a report of science experiments (that we've planned to go into), factual writing, and list.

Question 2: Do you also find that free choice of topics creates children who write gender stereotypes?

I think the experiences are more stereotyped. In grade 1 we still find that girls are more interested in some areas than boys. Boys are more interested in playing football and sorts of things. You'll find it in their writing, specially in early development when they are still recalling, recounting, read, record, what they have experienced. As they move on, it becomes less apparent. But, I just think that boys and girls are different and they will be interested in different things and we do have to try to take away that stereotypes that 's always around, but we still have to be aware of the fact that boys and girls are different and do have different interests.

Question 3: During the process of writing, particularly in revising stage, are your children able to revise and improve their writing?

The children who are developed more, in year 1 level, are beginning to become aware of that editing, and revising stage. I do it in my demonstration, that we revise, as a

group, and I'll write, and I'll get them to help me to write and revise. We find that the children at a high level are ready to do that at this stage in year one.

Question 4: Do you also think that the process approach advantages only a certain group of children? Do you find some children who do not succeed in their learning to write?

The ones who develop slow do need something extra. We give them a program which is an intensive program, when children learn to have sort of built skills in categorising, and some others just need to build up vocabularies. So, the children who have a go can go further, and those who struggle can at least express their ideas, which is very-very good.

Question 5: Do you find that the individualised program, like the process approach ignores the fact that writing is a social process/ activity?

What we're doing is that whenever they're doing writing, we are making sure that they are aware of why they are doing it. Sometimes it is a social thing for other people to write and to read. In addition you have to make it clear that the writing has the audience and purpose, and another time is just for their pleasure. So, it's dependent on when they are writing.

Teacher B

Question 1: In the process approach, where the children are allowed to write with the topic from their own, do you find your children write only stories with the same topic over and over again?

We must have some directive writing periods, with the broader writing program. Quite often that their choices are within the framework, looking at the theme we're doing at that particular time. Some children need more guides than the others. If they are repeating the same things over and over again, we need to give them some different stimuli that are getting them to think something different. Basically, our topics are

within the area that we are talking about. Sometimes free story writing, sometimes give them topic, let them express ideas but within the topic talked about.

To make the children write in different genre, we try to present them with a lot of models, nonfiction, showing them actual differences in nonfiction books, presenting them a different kind of genre, newspapers articles, etc.

Question 2: Do you also find that free choice of topics creates children who write gender stereotypes?

Oh, yes. The boys tend to write blooding, guns, and girls tend to write fantasy. So, we're trying to change that, to try to channel to another version, by putting limitations on their writing, like no killing, no blood, no shooting.

Question 3: During the process of writing, particularly in revising stage, are your children able to revise and improve their writing?

Some know better than others. Some struggle with it. Some of them don't like doing it. They feel off their writing, and that's it. We just keep encouraging them to read through their work and proofread it, check all the spelling and punctuation, does it make sense? do I like what I have written? Is it what I wanted to say?

With difficult spelling of the word, I get them to look at the words and say over to them, what sounds the words have. If they go through that process, the learning process is much better.

Question 4: Do you also think that the process approach advantages only a certain group of children? Do you find some children who do not succeed in their learning to write?

No, I have some children in my room now who have very limited vocabulary but they're still not afraid to put their thoughts down on paper. They'll have a go with the words that might be phonetically mistake, but they make sense of it. They're not afraid to make mistakes.

Question 5: Do you find that the individualised program, like the process approach ignores the fact that writing is a social process/ activity?

We do a variety of things. We might have a period of silent writing, where it's important that children write down on paper. We might also have a group of children brainstorming, working together, helping and learning from each other, in a large or a small group. In addition, the fact that you get the children to present what they've written to each other, help each other, share their writing with each other, means that there is a place for social practice. It's social in that way. Quite often that they're working within groups.

Teacher C

Question 1: In the process approach, where the children are allowed to write with the topic from their own, do you find your children write only stories with the same topic over and over again?

There are a lot of things that we do. Sometimes we give them a topic, sometimes they have a choice of two or three different pieces of writing, for example, of history, they might have to write a letter to someone back a hundred years ago, or they might have to write a review of the work we have been doing, and they might get a chance, in that session, to do one of those that they get the choice, but over the whole term or the whole year, they have to attempt to write each style of writing. So, free choice of topics does not create children who write only stories with the same topic over and over again. We do have some free choice writing, but they don't write the same story or the same topic over and over again.

Question 2: Do you also find that free choice of topics creates children who write gender stereotypes?

In some cases they do, yes, that's still the case in some. But we can get away with that by putting them into different contents, say, we're writing something where it's got two strong contents or characters for the same gender or two different genders. It's

always important that children have a different role models, and we have to give them models by choosing a story and make sure to them that that is not gendered bias.

Question 3: During the process of writing, particularly in revising stage, are your children able to revise and improve their writing?

They have to be taught, they have to be modelled all the time and many strategies have to be demonstrated. they should be encouraged to use their thinking, like editing their own spelling, using peers to read through and check their work as well, underlining things.

Question 4: Do you also think that the process approach advantages only a certain group of children? Do you find some children who do not succeed in their learning to write?

Some children perhaps are not up to grade level, but I don't think that there would be any difference, no matter which process you've been using. I think it really a case of addressing the child's problem, rather than we left them with the approach to teaching.

Question 5: Do you find that the individualised program, like the process approach ignores the fact that writing is a social process/ activity?

I don't think so, because we do have a great chance of making a social writing when we're doing a demonstration, when they're working with their peers, when they're having a conference together as a social writing, modelling to each other, and when they've finished, they're reading it, displaying it. Again, they're seeing each other's work, which in this sense is a social practice.